

Multi Sector Assessment MSA KANDAHAR

Nutrition Food Security WASH and Mortality in Kandahar
Province of Afghanistan during January-February 2017

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per Gemma

List of abbreviations

ACF	Action Contre la Faime, international NGO
AIM-WG	Assessment and Information Management - Working Group
BARAN	Afghan NGO
BF	Breastfeeding
BPHS	Basic Package of Health Services
CDR	Crude Death Rate
CI	Confidence Interval
CMAM	Community Management of Acute Malnutrition
DEFF	Design Effect
DoE	Department of Economy
DoPH	Department of Public Health
DoRRD	Department of Rural Rehabilitation and Development
ENA	Emergency Nutrition Assessment (freeware software) with related methods
EPI	Epidemiologic software (freeware) with related methods
F	Female
FS	Food Security
FCS	Food Consumption Index, food security score
GAM	General Acute Malnutrition
HAZ	Height for Age Z score, anthropometric index
HDDS	Household Dietary Diversity Score, food security index
HH	Household
HHS	Household Hunger Score, food security and awareness index
HRDA	Human Resources Development Agency (Afghan NGO)
IDP	Internally Displaced Person
IED	Improvised Explosive Device
INTERSOS	International NGO
IO	International Organization
IYCF	Infant and Young Children Feeding
KDH	Kandahar
M	Male
M	Mean (also "Average")
MAM	Moderate Acute Malnutrition
MEDAIR	International NGO
Median	Middle value in a series
MSA	Multi Sector Assessment
MUAC	Mid Upper Arm Circumference
NCC	Nutrition Cluster (Coordinator)
NGO	Non Governmental Organization
NSP	National Solidarity Program (of the World Bank)
OCHA	Office for Coordination of the Humanitarian Affairs
PD	Police (or Public) Department (urban cluster)

PPPS	Probability Proportional to Population Size (randomization method)
PPtS	Probability Proportional to Size (randomization method, same as above)
RUF/RUTF	Ready to Use (Therapeutic) Food
SADD	Sex and Age Disaggregated Data
SAM	Severe Acute Malnutrition
SD	Standard Deviation
SMART	Sensible Measurable Attainable Relevant Timely (mnemonic) Standardized Monitoring and Assessment of Relief and Transitions
SMART	(system)
StC	Save the Children
SUDAAN	Statistical Commercial Software
U5Y	Under 5 Years of Age child
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nation High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF	United Nations International Children Education Fund
WASH	Water And Sanitation Hygiene
WAZ	Weight for Age Z score, anthropometric index
WHO	World Health Organization
WHZ	Weight for Height Z score, anthropometric index
WWW	Who does What Where (sometime + WHW = When How and Why)
Z	Z scores, statistical index

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Executive summary

Kandahar Province in Southern Region of Afghanistan, cradle of Taleban movement and frequent theatre of armed fighting, has seen massive influx of IDP from neighbouring provinces (mainly Helmand and Uruzgan) as well as of Documented and Undocumented Returnees from Pakistan within the year 2016.

Such increase of frequently despoiled population over an already stressed Health System, facing restricted budget and accessibility issues, has the capacity to induce an alarmingly surge of morbidity, permanent disability and mortality. This especially within the most vulnerable: kids and mothers who are already enduring the consequences of 40 years of “chronic emergency” as a consequence of the longest armed conflict situation of modern history.

In order to collect fresh and reliable data to plan emergency humanitarian intervention the INTERSOS international NGO established a partnership with Human Resources Development Association (HRDA) national Afghan NGO, to realize the present MSA or Multi Sector Assessment in Kandahar. Objects of the assessment are to rapidly collect relevant population, nutrition, food security, WASH and mortality data/indicators from the target population.

We utilized demographic data obtained by the NSP database (November 2016 update). The geographic area covered does include all the 17 province’s districts. First level security analysis has been conducted at village level with the aid of local experts and community facilitators. From this analysis 414 villages within the 17 districts have been considered “Insecure” enough not to be included in the selection database to be sampled for assessment. We then performed a “phase 1” survey in the 9 central districts considered “middle to low level on insecurity” followed by a “phase 2” - with highly improved mitigation procedures in place - in the remaining 8 more remote districts, considered at “high level of insecurity”. With these preliminary considerations the final sampled geo-demographic target resulted as follows:

Level	Sampled	Total in the Province	Sampled %
Districts	17	17	100
Villages/PDs	1,577	1,990	79.2
Families	281,318	363,259	77.4
Population	1,890,332	2,505,523	75.4

After proper planning, training and preparations the survey has been field performed from January 01 to 11 (phase1) and from February 5 to 15 (phase2) of 2017 by 6 teams of enumerators (1 male and 2 females in each team). Data collection, digitalization and analysis started in real time within the first day of field operations.

Methodology used two stage random cluster sampling: i) first stage cluster as village (if rural) or Police Department (if urban), random selection by software PtS i.e. Proportional to Size method; ii) second stage household random sampling using the SMART-modified EPI field method.

Data have been collected on programmed Excel spreadsheet and transferred to ENA 2011 software for further analysis.

MSA assessment includes:

- ✓ **77 clusters** (Rural villages or urban PDs) from 17 districts
- ✓ **504 households/questionnaires** (86.3% in rural villages – 13.7% in urban PDs)
- ✓ **6,252 persons** (with 1,720 children under 5 years of age)
- ✓ **1,492 anthropometries** in children 6-59 months of age

Main outcomes are as following:

If not differently specified all presented results are based on WHO standards 2006 reference table with SMART flag exclusions for extreme un-plausible value applied by ENA software 2011, release July 2015. All Confidence Interval at 95% (CI⁹⁵) and Design Effects (DEFF) calculated by ENA software SUDAAN procedure if not differently specified. When specified (as CI^{95T}) the Confidence Intervals have been calculated by the Central Limit Theorem formula for quasi-normal (n>30) distribution.

Acute Malnutrition prevalence in 6-59 months of age children with CI⁹⁵			
based on WHZ	All	Boys	Girls
General Acute Malnutrition (<-2 Zs) GAM	8.8 6.0 - 12.8 %	10.6 7.2 - 15.4 %	7.4 6.9 - 10.7 %
Severe Acute Malnutrition (<-3 Zs) SAM	1.1 0.5 - 2.2 %	1.6 0.7 - 3.6%	0.5 0.2 - 1.5 %
based on MUAC	All	Boys	Girls
General Acute Malnutrition (<125mm) GAM	14.4 11.8 - 17.5 %	14.5 11.4 - 18.3 %	14.3 11.0 - 18.5 %
Severe Acute Malnutrition (<115mm / oedema) SAM	3.4 2.4 - 4.7 %	3.4 2.2 - 5.3 %	3.4 2.1 - 5.3 %
combined criteria WHZ+MUAC (CI^{95T})	All	Boys	Girls
General Acute Malnutrition (<125mm, <-2Zs) GAM	16.5 14.4 - 18.5 %	17.5 14.6 - 20.4 %	15.5 12.7 - 18.3 %
Severe Acute Malnutrition (<115mm, <-3Zs) SAM	3.4 2.4 - 4.4 %	3.6 2.2 - 5.0 %	3.4 2.0 - 4.8 %

Chronic Malnutrition prevalence in 6-59 months of age children with CI⁹⁵			
Underweight	All	Boys	Girls
General Underweight WAZ – 2 Zs	23.5 19.9 - 27.7%	26.6 22.4 - 31.4%	20.4 16.0 - 25.5%
Severe Underweight WAZ <3 Zs	6.7 5.2 - 8.6%	7.2 5.0 - 10.1%	6.2 4.4 - 8.7 %
Stunting	All	Boys	Girls
General Stunting WHZ <2 Zs	53.2 49.6 - 56.6%	54.1 50.0 - 58.2%	52.2 46.8 - 57.6 %
Severe Stunting WHZ <3Zs	22.7 19.5 - 26.3 %	24.2 20.6 - 28.3%	21.3 17.1 - 26.2%

Mortality n deaths/10,000/day with CI⁹⁵ and Design Effect			
Crude Mortality Rate:	All	Male (cases)	Female(cases)
in General population	0.96 0.72 – 1.29 DEFF 1.48	# 44	# 28
in Under <5 years old	1.12 0.64 – 1.94 DEFF 1.62	# 10	# 12

Population of the sample:			
Urban 13.7%		Rural 86.3%	
Residents 75.8%	IDP 17.3%	Doc.-Returnees 1.2%	Undoc.-Returnees 2.0%
Accessibility to Health Services (1 hour):		24.0% (CI ^{95%} 20.3 - 27.7)	
Perception of malnutrition in the Household:		1.5% (CI ^{95%} 0.4 - 2.6)	

Household Nutrition and Food Security		
HDDS Household Dietary Diversity Score:	4.3 ± 2.0	(M±SD)
FCS Food Consumption Score:	50.5 ± 32.1	(M±SD)
FCS < 35 (in % of households)	17.1%	(CI ^{95%} 13.8 - 20.4)
Single primary source of foods:	31.0%	
Single secondary source of foods:	15.5%	
Double Source of foods:	34.1%	
HHS Household Hunger Score:	8.1 ± 5.3	(M±SD)

Water and Sanitation Hygiene		
Water Access > 500 meters from home	18.1%	(CI ^{95%} 14.7 - 21.5)
Open air latrines	33.7%	(CI ^{95%} 29.6 - 37.8)
Minimum correct hand washing procedures	20.7%	(CI ^{95%} 17.2 - 24.2)

Breastfeeding and Vaccinations practices		
Early Breastfeeding 1h after birth	48.2%	(CI ^{95%} 43.8 - 52.6)
Exclusive Breastfeeding in the first 6 months	26.8%	(CI ^{95%} 22.9 - 30.7)
Demonstrated full vaccination coverage (booklet)	22.0%	(CI ^{95%} 18.4 - 25.6)

The **high Prevalence of Acute and Chronic Malnutrition** and the **high Mortality Rates**, both approaching or surpassing the conventional emergency thresholds, suggests the necessity of an emergency humanitarian intervention.

Given the **multiple burdens observed** in Access to Health Services, Perception of Disease, Health Education, Household Nutrition, Food Security and WASH the best approach for a **Humanitarian Intervention should be comprehensive. Actions to ensure sustainability and enduring benefits, like education, shall be included to help overcoming the “chronic emergency” problem.**

With Statistical Analysis, different outcomes (high Dispersion Index, WHZ DEFF >4, Poisson test highly significant) indicates in-homogeneity within the sample, with **presence of “pockets of higher gaps and suffering”** reaching emergency level of needs, where to address the first priority humanitarian aids.

Now, the geo-demographic unit of this assessment (i.e. “cluster”) is the village, whilst the unit generally utilized for planning (at NGO level at least) it is the district.

In the process of reconciling the village cluster sampling with the district level of planning we made an exercise of mapping the outcomes of this assessment on the Kandahar Province’s territory crossing different data set at cluster (village) and district level related to:

- a) Higher prevalence of acute and chronic malnutrition
- b) Higher mortality rates and causes of death
- c) Higher percentage of non residents (mainly IDPs) in the total population

- d) Lower level of Health education
- e) Worst situation in terms of WASH and Food Security
- f) Lower presence of Health Facilities and of Nutritional Services

Then taking into considerations the population figures, accessibility (in terms of geographical as well as security constraints) plus general feasibility and relevance of interventions, after consultation with local authorities we came out with this mapping:

We thus identified the districts of Maywand, Nesh and Reg to be the worst affected (red purple codes) followed by Zhari, Daman, Maruf, Shaga and Shawalikot (red codes). We need further informations from Shorabak and Ghorak (grey color)¹. The other areas orange: Panjiway, Spin Boldak, Arghistan then yellow codes: Khakriz, Miya Nishin, Arghandab and Kandahar have as well - of course - high levels of unattended needs and further “pockets of suffering” but if a priority shall be made at district level we will identify the above mentioned as the first ones where to plan humanitarian emergency actions.

¹ Cluster randomization at village level didn't included villages form these two districts.

1. Introduction²

Geographic description of survey area

- Afghanistan, Southern Region, Kandahar Province, Area 54,022 Km²
- 17 Districts totally
- We distinguished two zones, based on accessibility related to insecurity level

a) *High Insecurity Area*: 8 districts, red zones in the map

Arghistan
Ghorak
Kakhriz
Maruf
Miya Neshin
Nish
Reg
Shorabak

b) *Low / Middle Insecurity Area*: 9 districts, orange zones in the map

Kandahar
Daman
Shah Wali Kot
Arghandab
Maywand
Panjiway
Spin Boldak
Zhari
Shaga (also called Taktapul)

² Geo-demographic and general information in this chapter comes directly from local sources, meetings, interviews and exchanges done December 2016: Dept. of Public Health Kandahar (DoPH), Dept of Economy Kandahar (DoE), UN-OCHA Southern Region, UNHCR, IoM, plus Baran, MSF, Medair and Save the Children ngo.

- 1,990 rural villages or “PD” Police Departments” if in urban area (see complete list of villages and PDs in appendix)
- 70% rural setting, 30% urban, presence of scattered informal camps
- semi-desert terrain
- continental hot-dry climate with very hot summers and comfortable winters
- survey carried on in winter season (January-February)

Description of the population

- 2,505,523 persons living in the surveyed area
- Muslims
- Pashto language
- Pashtuns, with tiny minority of Tajiks, Hazaras, Uzbeks and Baloch in the city
- Mixed: residents / IDPs, with minority of documented and undocumented returnees
- High influx of IDP, conflict driven, mainly from Hilmand and Uruzgan trough 2016
- IDPs in Afghanistan take shelter with host communities or in informal settlement; their numbers are difficult to ascertain and tend to be underestimated because they do not include all IDPs living in urban areas, who are often dispersed among economic migrants and the urban poor and so are difficult to identify. They also exclude IDPs in hard to access rural areas across all regional districts. Nor are exhaustive data available on former refugees (i.e.”returnees”, documented or undocumented) unable or unwilling to return to their places of origin.
- Major livelihoods in the area: agriculture, pastoralist
- High level of unemployment in urban area

Services and humanitarian assistance

- Basic Package of Health Services BPHS implementer is BARAN NGO
- BARAN last three years SAM-OPD nutrition activity (in appendix)
- Relief programmes in area: see attached OCHA WWW Dec 2016 (in appendix)
- MEDAIR is carrying on a nutrition project with Mobile Nutrition Clinics focused on IDP settlements in the Kandahar central area districts of the province
- Save the Children terminated in November 2016 a nutrition project in cooperation with BARAN in Health Facilities
- Presence of Health Services “white areas” (handmade HRDA map in appendix)
- Mixed quality of roads: from good paved road to mountain trails
- Access to markets conditioned by the volatile security situation

Security

- Low intensity guerrilla / terrorist attack / targeted killing chronic conflict situation
- Around 50% of the provincial territory in rural area not in Government control
- IEA Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan (the Taleban) “Laya” Code of Conduct document and recent statements by main chain of Command and Control declared humanitarian NGOs as not-acceptable targets
- Independent Armed Opposition Groups acting out of control of main Taleban movement, as well as ACG Armed Criminal Groups, maintain a dangerous presence in the area and in the city of Kandahar

1.1 Survey Objectives

Precondition:

- Segregate as much as possible all human-person related data over sex, age and diverse abilities
- Keep respect of privacy and INTERSONS/HRDA ethical codes of conduct

Survey Primary Objectives

- Estimate prevalence of General Acute Malnutrition GAM and Severe Acute Malnutrition SAM in children of age 6 to 59 months
- Estimate Crude Death Rate CDR in population and CDR in children under 5 years of age

Secondary Objectives

- Estimate Underweight and Stunting prevalence in children of age 6 to 59 months
- Evaluate Residential status: segregate Resident, Internal Displaced Persons IDP, Documented or Undocumented Returnees from foreign countries (in generally form Pakistan)
- Evaluate Family composition, age pyramid and household average persons size
- Evaluate House building structure
- Evaluate perception of Malnutrition and Disability
- Evaluate perceived Accessibility to Health Services
- Food Security: measure Household Dietary Diversity Score HDDS, Food Consumption Score FCS with variety of food sources and Household Hunger Score HHS
- Evaluate Vaccinations coverage and vaccination's Awareness
- Breast Feeding BF: evaluate prevalence of early initiation of BF<1h after birth and the practice of exclusive BF in the children <6months of age
- WASH: prevalence of water access < 500 meters from home,
source of water
kind of latrines
hand washing practices

2. Methodology

The Assessment was originally planned to be performed in the 9 central districts of *Low / Middle Insecurity Area* (orange zones in the map: First Phase). However following request by the Nutrition Cluster to extend the assessment to the whole Province's territory we added the remaining *High Insecurity Area*, 8 districts (red zones in the map: Second Phase).

The Second Phase was performed utilizing the same methodology, the same already trained teams of enumerators, same questionnaires, instruments, field instructions for questionnaires and anthropometries, but it required modified logistic and highly increased security mitigation procedures, as it will be further specified.

First Phase (January 1-11, 2017)

2.1 Sample size

- cross sectional random cluster sampling methodology, two stages:
 1st stage = village/PD level - with full population figures (ENA software)
 2nd stage = household (EPI system SMART modified)
 If necessary (more households under the same roof) 3rd stage random selection one the households (names of possible respondents on small pieces of paper and blind selection)
- Anthropometry and Mortality sample sizes calculated by software ENA: input parameters as follows

Parameter	Value	Source / Rationale
GAM estimated	10%	StC SMART 2014 (Medair SMART 2016 = 7.7%)
Precision	3%	Related to estimated prevalence and targets
Design effect	2.0	Population Urban/Rural and includes non residents
Avr. Family / HH*	6.7 / 12.0	Specific NSP database (Nov 2016) # pop / # families
U5Y	23%*	From HRDA & INTERSOS field test in KDH Jan 2017
Non responders	3%	As from previous experiences
Outcome =	836	Children 6-59mths to check (+10% prudential = 920)
CDR estimated	0.2	StC SMART 2014
Precision	0.2	Based on estimated CDR
Design effect	1.6	Population includes Urban/Rural and non residents
Non responders	3%	A from previous experiences
Recall period	111	From Eid ul Adha (Sept 11 2016)
Outcome =	3014	Persons to be included for CDR

- Estimated GAM based on previous assessments (SMART by Save the Children Kandahar 2014; MEDAIR Kandahar Sept 2016), required precision 3%, Design Effect DEFF = 2.0 based on the observation of different groups within the sample (Urban vs Rural, Residents vs Non-residents = IDP, Returnees Documented or Undocumented)

- Number of children per household: official average family Kandahar Province (from NSP National Solidarity Program – WB - database = 6.7. However family is NOT same as household: definition household = “group of people living (=sleeping) under the same roof and eating from the same kitchen pot”. In AFN frequently encountered are more families under the same roof. We did a pilot field test in two villages nearby Kandahar as part of the training: Tamanian and Kulcha Abad. Result =

Children under 5 years of age or U5Y = 23%.

Average household size = 12.0

Children under 5 x Household = 12 x 0.23 = 2.76

Expected # households = 920 / 2.76 = 334

These values we used for planning. ENA planning screenshot is attached:

Planning Nutrition Survey

Name of Survey: AFN-1701-KDH-Intersos-HRDA-FI

Sampling: Random Cluster

Correction small population size

Sample size calculation for a cross sectional anthropometric survey*

Estimated prevalence %: 10 | Average household size: 12
 ± desired precision %: 3 | % children under 5: 23
 Design effect: 2.0 | % of non-response households: 3
 Children to be included: 836 | Households to be included: 347

Sample size calculation for a death rate survey*

Estimated death rate per 10,000/day: 0.2 | Average household size: 12
 ± desired precision per 10,000/day: 0.2 | % of non-response households: 3
 Design effect: 1.6 | Recall period in days: 111
 Population to be included: 3014 | Households to be included: 259

*Please change the default values to get more correct estimations for the sample size

Table for Cluster sampling

Population Size: 1625527

Geographical unit	Population size	Cluster
Amarat	1204	
Bilandai	2370	
Chaplanai	3240	
Deh Ghulaman	1190	
Deh Rajab	2439	
Arazi	1176	
Gurgan	1050	
Kalantar	2450	
Kohkaran	1496	
Khan Agha Qalacha	2100	
Kakarano Goush Khana	1330	1

Number of Clusters: 52 | Assign Cluster

Random Number Table

Range from to Numbers | Generate Table

- Sample size for mortality calculated by ENA software. Expected CDR (from previous SMART 2014 done by StC = 0.2 d/10,000/die. Required precision 0.2 DEFF: 1.6 (similar reasons as above); recall period 111 days (from Eid ul Adha).
- 3% non-responders adjustment based on previous assessments same area.
- expected # of household for mortality = 259. Being the # households higher in anthropometry, we used the anthropometry one
- Workforce-workload calculation: we calculated 180' die of operational assessment time based on the following table:

0800-0830	0830-0930	0930-1230	1230-1330	1330-1430	1430-1600
Briefing Preparing	Travel GO 60'	HH Assesment time	Break/lunch	Travel BACK	Debriefing Resetting GPS Re-equipping
30'	60'	180'	60'	60'	90'

Then field-tested and measured on the base of:

- 1) our developed questionnaire,
 - 2) the average of 2-3 children in the range age per household,
 - 3) the field test anthropometries timing (10')
- a capacity of:

1 Questionnaire / HH + 2 anthropometries in 18'-20' i.e.

9 questionnaires / 20 anthropometries per day per team

Need of 920 anthropometries / 20 = 46 clusters

Operational Logistic Target = 1 cluster per day per team

6 field teams: 46/6 = 7.6 (=8) days of field work

So we decided to do the field assessment on this requirements:

- ✓ At least **920 anthropometries** in ...
- ✓ at least **334 households** / questionnaires describing
- ✓ at least **4008 persons** in ...
- ✓ at least 46 (we added a prudential + 6 clusters) **total 52 clusters**
- ✓ by the way of **6 teams** on 52 cluster in 5+4=**9 days** of field work

2.2 Sampling procedure: selecting clusters

- Population figures has been taken from NSP National Solidarity Program database, November 2016 update, Kandahar Province full data, village level
- 52 (+ 6 "Reserve Clusters" RC) were randomly selected by ENA software according to PPPS i.e. Probability Proportional to Population Size procedure.

District	Village	Population	Cluster
Kandahar	Kakarano Goush Khana	1330	1
Kandahar	Zakar Sharif	10000	2
Kandahar	Naw Deh	1652	3
Kandahar	Gundigan	1400	4
Kandahar	Ghulam Dastageer Qalacha	1932	5
Kandahar	Ganj Qalacha	735	6
Kandahar	Mohammad Gull Qalacha	2205	RC
Daman	Dai Kalai	1366	7
Daman	Mandisar	3510	8
Daman	Zaker Abad	1056	9

Shah Wali Kot	Wali	2427	10
Shah Wali Kot	Shada	1184	11
Shah Wali Kot	Sozanai Asikzai	830	12
Shah Wali Kot	Hajji Payoo Aka Kalai	1349	13
Arghandab	Khwaja Malk	2472	14
Arghandab	Kocha Nagahan	1300	15
Arghandab	Dasht Masjed	1400	16
Maywand	Safozai Kalai	2100	17
Maywand	Kariz Wal	1050	18
Maywand	Da Qalachai Kalai	656	19
Maywand	Hayatullah Kalai	1011	20
Maywand	Fida Mohammad Kariz	700	21
Maywand	Da Zarei Walaswali Kalai	770	22
Panjwayi	Bal Ghour Abdul Mohammad	917	23
Panjwayi	Gul Agha Kalai	1855	24
Panjwayi	Tajdar	821	25
Panjwayi	Abdul Ghani	2139	26
Panjwayi	Hajji Amanullah	1316	27
Panjwayi	Hajji Baridad	1054	RC
Panjwayi	Madina	941	28
Spin Boldak	Haji Gud Kalai	875	29
Spin Boldak	Hazrat Bilal	2198	30
Spin Boldak	Sahib Jan	1488	31
Spin Boldak	Barakzo Kalai	1281	32
Spin Boldak	Haji Mohammad Mosa	2198	33
Spin Boldak	Abdul Gapor	1297	RC
Spin Boldak	Mirhamza Abdul Gapor	2169	34
Spin Boldak	Abdul Jabar Zhara Ghberga`	1566	35
Spin Boldak	Hajji Fida Mohammad Kalai	1572	36
Spin Boldak	Abdul	2044	37
Spin Boldak	Mandai Pahlawan	1960	38
Spin Boldak	Pakhwaran	1957	39
Spin Boldak	Sidano Kaly	1645	RC
Spin Boldak	Toor Shadi	2156	40
Spin Boldak	Da Dolai Shora Rabat	2170	RC
Spin Boldak	Hajji Akhter Mohammad	1083	41
Spin Boldak	Abdul Malik & Mohammad Esa	1750	42
Spin Boldak	Mullah Rahmatullah	2135	43
Zhari	Eid Gah	1800	44
Zhari	Paında	1140	45
Zhari	Omarzai	1710	46
Zhari	Lawar Baghan Jai	1770	47
Zhari	Hajji Fiaz Mohammad Aka/ Shachoi	1722	RC

Zhari	Da Shahidano Baba Da Ghra Shata Kalai/Sanzarai	1374	48
Zhari	Nabatullah Kalai / Sartak	1174	49
Zhari	Sadiqullah Kalai / Dasht	1850	50
Shaga	Fatawi Kalai	1010	51
Shaga	Fati Khan Lwar Mail	657	52

- A total of 53 clusters have been actually visited during the survey; 6 assigned clusters being substituted by the 6 RC “Reserve Clusters” due to in-deep real time risk-analysis with local experts related to changing security conditions.

2.3 Sampling procedure: selecting households and children

- Clusters’ households have been selected according to EPI, SMART-modified procedure. Arriving in the centre of the cluster (village if rural or “PD” Police Department if urban) the team supervisor/leader performed the following:
 - a) take GPS position then “off” and leave the instrument in the car
 - b) spin a pen on the ground
 - c) walk all the way indicated by the pen tip to the edge of the village/PD
 - d) spin again the pen until it shows a direction toward the village
 - e) check the random table 30x30 given to him as part of the daily equipment
 - f) walk the direction indicated by the pen
 - g) identify the first household according to the first suitable random number
 - h) then do the next household to the right
 - i) Then again and again to the right until you reach at least 20 anthropometries

This system was used in all clusters

- Empty households or households with absent children were re-visited in all cases where it was not evidently abandoned houses
- Empty or non-responding households were registered in all cases and the team went on in the assessment until the minimum number of 20 anthropometries per cluster per day was reached
- All eligible children in range in visited households have been weighted and measured
- Survey respondents were spontaneously selected within the household according to who wanted to respond to the questionnaire

2.4 Case definitions and inclusion criteria

- Definition of the household: Group of people living (= habitually sleeping) under the same roof and eating from the same kitchen pot
- Age range of the children included in anthropometry survey was 6 to 59 months
- If age was unknown decision to include children was based on height 65 to 100cm
- Cut-off for deciding whether the height of the child should be measured standing up or laying down was 87 cm

- Case definition for GAM and SAM:

WHZ <-2	(SAM <-3)
MUAC <125mm	(SAM < 115mm)
Oedema	(SAM = +)

Oedema objectivated by visual plus tactile touch and gentel pressing, bilateral both feet and lower legs +
lower body ++
all body +++
- WHO-2006 standards used to report anthropometry results
- Recall period in mortality survey 111 days
- Well-known event used to explain to survey responders the date of the start of recall period was the important Muslim festivity of Eid-ul-Adha (Sept 11 2016).
- The respondent for all questions was the same, in case of need she/he was able to get help from other households persons.
- Households with no eligible children for anthropometry were included in mortality survey

2.5 Questionnaire, training and supervision

Questionnaire

- Questionnaire used in the field was in Pashto language
- Interviews in the field were conducted in Pashto language
- The questionnaire has been translated and back-translated by a different translator before the survey
- The questionnaire has been widely pre-tested in classroom as well as twice piloted in the field before the survey. Moreover a similar questionnaire has been recently used by INTERSOS in our internal evaluation of the Italian Cooperation funded pilot nutrition comprehensive project in Hirat Province
- Copies of the questionnaire in English and in Pashto are included in the Appendices

Survey teams and supervision

- Composition of the survey team was as follows
6 teams of 3 persons (1 male team leader + 2 female enumerators)
2 data entry clerks (trained with field teams and acting as “field reserves” if necessary)
2 trainers - supervisors (dr Ehsan Yawan and dr Ali Stanikzai)
1 trainer - coordinator (Dr Giorgio M Cortassa)
- 6 teams were trained, and 6 teams participated in the survey
- All the survey workers were well literate in Pashto and in basic English, 60% of them were professional health workers (doctors, nurses or midwives; there was always at least one professional health worker in all teams)
- 2 team supervisors participated in the survey
- Dr Ehsan Yawan is MD, HoP of HRDA ngo, 10 years of clinical and managerial medical experience in Afghanistan, plus multiple field assessments experience in his work as Head of Programs HRDA ngo, Kandahar
- Dr Ali Stanikzai is MD, 25 years of clinical medical experience in Afghanistan, multiple experiences in medical and nutritional related field assessments,

participated to NNS survey, previous experience as medical officer of BARAN ngo, vast knowledge of urban and rural environment of Kandahar Province

- Dr Giorgio M Cortassa is MD, Specialist Internal Medicine (eq. Phd), Specialist Metabolic Diseases (Eq Phd.), 33 years experience clinical medicine, 10+ years experience International Cooperation, Project Coordinator, previous experience Afghanistan 2003 (AMI NGO, coordianteur medicale nationale) extensive nutrition assessments carried on in Tibetan AR in previous mission assignments 2006.
- Survey teams were distant supervised at all times and they were field supervised as deemed necessary: 1 supervisor / 3 teams

Training

- Training for survey teams was conducted by dr Eshan, dr Ali and dr Giorgio
- The training covered: general survey objectives, overview of survey design, household selection procedures, anthropometric measurements, signs and symptoms of malnutrition, data collection and interview skills, mortality interview, role playing simulations, questionnaire testing chronometry and validation, GPS training, interviews skills, pilot filed test #1 and #2 at village level, security mitigation procedures, geographic cluster per cluster risk analysis
- The anthropometry standardization exercise was conducted as part of the training: 11 children in the age range measured per each enumerator
- Duration of the training was 6 days per 6 hours = 36 hours total
- Two field pre-test has been conducted in nearby villages Tamanan and Kulcha Abad; 18+18 children and / 12+12 households have been included in the pre-test
- Training schedule is included in appendix

2.6 Data analysis

- Two clerks daily entered collected data in an ad-hoc programmed Excel worksheet. The data were then daily transferred to ENA software and pre-analysed by dr Stanikzai and by dr Cortassa
- Quality control procedures were double data entry by two clerks, plus random checks on around 10% of entered records, plus daily ENA software analysis including plausibility test.
- Excel MS 2007 ad hoc programmed plus ENA 2011 July 2015 release were used
- Outliers in anthropometry data were excluded from the analysis according to SMART flags, i.e. +/- 3 SD of WHZ, WAZ, HAZ from the observed Z means
- As it is not culturally acceptable in Afghanistan to perform anthropometries on naked children this was done with the child wearing minimum winter type undergarments. We pre-checked with precision scale this type of clothes weight from 22 children of the different ages included in the range (average 26 months) finding average value 52 ± 18 . We used 52g as correction weight in ENA.

NB:

- field equipment included: i) measuring table, UNICEF-approved type, ii) precision scale electronic, SECA brand, UNICEF-approved type, iii) MUAC measuring strip UNICEF-approved type, iv) GPS Garmin Etrex type + 2 spare NiMh batteries
- Scales were daily checked for accuracy down to 100g against standard weights
- UNICEF-approved equipment kindly given us freely to be used by BARAN NGO
- Given the fact that the greatest majority of respondents (>90%) was not able to identify the birthday of the child we decided to indicate this age in months

Second Phase (February 2-15, 2017)

2.7 General procedure, logistic and insecurity mitigation measures

As previously stated the Second Phase was performed utilizing the same general methodology, same already trained teams of enumerators, same questionnaires, instruments, field instructions for questionnaires and anthropometries, but it required modified logistic and highly increased security mitigation procedures, as follows:

- Not feasible daily return to HQ because of distance, road conditions and time for transfers: then necessary overnight planning in pre-selected safe locations
- The team was always accompanied in field by local well known and respected personnel
- The objectives, planning, timing and operational modalities of the Second Phase assessment were previously exhaustively discussed and agreed with local arbabs and shura representatives and the Communities were well informed of the procedure
- Roads to approach and leave the field / clusters have been discussed and agreed with security experts at local level
- Security assessment at village level has been further scrutinized and revised as necessary
- Field time exposure has been reduced
- GPSs have NOT be utilized in Phase 2 for security reasons³.
- Contingency planning were prepared

We faced delays up to 48h to reach some of the clusters due to the necessity to avoid main (dangerous) roads in relation to the known presence of multiple IEDs. Apart this no incidents occurred to the teams during the procedures.

2.8 Second phase ENA planning and random clusters selection

Second phase sampling included the 8 remaining “High Insecurity” districts (*Arghistan, Ghorak, Kakhriz, Maruf, Miya Neshin, Nish, Reg, Shorabak*).

Of the total 494 villages present in this area 286 villages have been considered not safe enough to perform the field assessment by Kandahar’s and local (District level) security experts; the remaining 208 villages have been considered at an acceptable level of security and included for the random selection (see list in appendices).

We used the planning parameters field-obtained from “Phase 1”, as follows:

- GAM estimated prevalence 15%
- Desired precision 3%
- DEFF 1.5
- Average HH size 12.0
- Children <5 = 23%
- Non responders: 3%
- Estimated CDR 0.9/10k/day
- And recall period was increased from 111 to 142 days

We calculated to add 24 clusters to the assessments, with an average of 18 anthropometries, or 5 questionnaires/households per clusters, performed by 6 teams (each team of three enumerators - 1 M + 2F members – plus one local “facilitator”) within 5 days of valid field work (timeframe of the field assessment is larger - 2 to 15 - due to holidays and described delays).

³ GPS have been only utilized in Phase 1, for which we have coordinates of all clusters.

Screenshot for ENA planning Phase 2 is attached:

Files Extras

Planning Training Data Entry Anthropometry Results Anthropometry Death Rates Food Security Options

Survey Protocol

Planning Nutrition Survey

Name of Survey
AFN-KDH-INTRS-HRDA-F2

Sampling
 Random Cluster
 Correction small population size

Sample size calculation for a cross sectional anthropometric survey*

15 Estimated prevalence % 12 Average household size
 5 ± desired precision % 23 % children under 5
 1.5 Design effect 3 % of non-response households
 320 Children to be included 133 Households to be included

Sample size calculation for a death rate survey*

0.9 Estimated death rate per 10,000/day
 0.5 ± desired precision per 10,000/day
 1.5 Design effect 12 Average household size
 142 Recall period in days 3 % of non-response households
 1590 Population to be included 137 Households to be included

*Please change the default values to get more correct estimations for the sample size

Table for Cluster sampling

Population Size: 233160

Geographical unit	Population size	Cluster
Darweshan	2163	
Balochan	1883	
Khoshi Kalai	2044	1
Kaido Kalai	2016	
Landai Now Abad	2184	
Hajji Abdul Bari Kariz	923	
Mohammad Sadiq Kariz	897	
?Qolba	979	
Wazir Kalai	511	
Hajji Dilbar Aka Kariz	704	2
Baidak	909	

RC: Reserve Cluster
 Number of Clusters: 24 Assign Cluster

Random Number Table

Range from to Numbers
 Generate Table

This results in an indication for 320 more children to be included within and expected more 133 household/questionnaires, plus 1590 more people within 137 household / questionnaires for the CDR component.

With 24 cluster x 18 anthropometries we planned for 432 more children to be included in the nutrition assessment, and with 24 clusters x 5 questionnaires/households x 12 persons/households we planned for more 120 households / 1440 people to be included in the CDR calculations (so slightly less than what required for an isolated assessment but enough if considered that the Phase 1 and Phase 2 data will be merged in a single survey).

List of randomized clusters by ENA PPS selection (24 clusters + 3 “reserve” clusters) it is as follows.

NB: cluster numbers have been relabelled +2nn (201 - 202 - 203 ... etc to distinguish them from the ones of Phase 1)

District	Village	Population	Cluster
Khakrez	Khoshi Kalai	2044	201
Khakrez	Hajji Dilbar Aka Kariz	704	202
Reg	Grang Sah	1713	203
Reg	Moula Dad Mir Alam Ato Kalai	1814	204
Reg	Sardar Mohammad Naim Kalai	1770	205
Arghistan	Ali Khanzai	1831	206
Arghistan	Narin Wala	1148	207

Arghistan	Sor Gaz	790	RC
Arghistan	Da Sar Kalai	1767	208
Arghistan	Asakzai	528	209
Arghistan	Popalzai	980	210
Arghistan	Sartif Kalawal Kalai	241	211
Maruf	Lowar Shekhzai	1365	212
Maruf	Abtoo Bahlolzai	595	213
Maruf	Sra Shela	11910	214
Maruf	Landai	496	215
Maruf	Angizai	1132	216
Maruf	Koli	1820	217
Maruf	Karim Kali	1080	218
Maruf	Jalal	522	219
Miya Nishin	Paynawa Zamto	2671	220
Miya Nishin	Low Tala Kalai	3812	221
Miya Nishin	Mazar Kalai Shora	2274	RC
Miya Nishin	Chako Gak	2693	222
Nesh	Sardagh	1427	223
Nesh	Kochnai Kariz	1142	224
Nesh	Podina	1610	RC

All 24 clusters have been visited during the survey. No substitution was necessary.

Merging Phase 1 and Phase 2

All collected data (Phase 1 + 2) have been digitalized in a programmed Excel Spreadsheet. From this file - by the use of filters and logic formulas – it is possible to analyze the whole package and/or to extract segregated data for single variables as district – household – residential condition (resident versus IDP or returnees) – family composition – sexes – house structure – etc.

Regarding the anthropometry and crude death rate section we used the “merge surveys” function included in the ENA software to obtain outcomes for a single unified full Kandahar provincial level nutrition assessment. For the CDR the recall period has been averaged to 120 days between the Phase 1 (111 days) and the Phase 2 (142 days) taking into consideration the proportionally greater number of people (4312) in Phase 1⁴.

Then separated nutrition and CDR results for Phase 1 and 2 are available as well as separated segregated outcomes for single variables as Residents versus Non-residents, Rural versus Urban population or single districts or groups of districts. Results from Phase 1 only are attached in appendices. It shall be pointed out that Phase 2 has been planned as an add-on to Phase 1 and not as a stand-alone survey.

Whenever not differently specified the following results are referred to the entire Kandahar province (Phase 1+ 2) whole survey.

⁴ $X = (\text{Population F1} \times 111) + (\text{Population F2} \times 142) / \text{Population F3}; [(4312 \times 111) + (1940 \times 142)] / 6252 = 120$

3. Results

We collected data from **77 clusters** (53 in Phase 1 and 24 in Phase 2) a total of 504 questionnaires each one related to one household i.e.

- ✓ **504 households** including a total of
- ✓ **6252 persons** i.e.
- ✓ **12.4** average persons per household, and performed
- ✓ **1441 anthropometries** on children in age range 6-59 months

Non respondents: (14) = **2.8%**

Respondent: Sex Female = (484) **96.0%**; **Age** (M±SD = 41.6±14.9) Median **39 years**

In 91.9% of cases the respondent did not identified herself as the “head fo the family”.

Head of family: Sex Male = (458) **90.9%**; **Age** (M±SD = 51.6±15.8) Median **49 years**

Household Urban vs Rural position:

Position	Urban	Rural
#	69	435
%	13.7	86.3

Household Residential status:

	Residents	IDP	Documented Returnees	Unocumented Returnees
#	382	87	6	10
%	75.8	17.3	1.2	2.0

N: missing data from 19 HH (3.7%)

House Structure:

kind of	Shelter ⁵	Tent	Mud	Brick	Apartment
#	3	9	397	72	4
%	0.6	1.8	78.8	14.3	0.8

Accessibility to Health Services (1hour):

Answer	Yes	No: Distance	No: Money
#	121	321	44
%	24.0	63.7	8.7

The question was: “In the case somebody here would be acutely sick, just now, can we reach an health facility within 1 hour?” If: “Yes“: ok, stop. If: “Not” = then: “Why?” and choices: Distance problem / Money Problem / Other problems

⁵ N*: temporary repair made by plastic sheeting, discarded housing materials or similar arrangements

Age Ranges / Sex:

<6M	<6F	6-59M	6-59F	5-18M	5-18F	18-50M	18-50F	>50M	>50F
120	84	724	792	954	1009	975	1029	335	230
1.9%	1.3%	11.6%	12.7%	15.3%	16.1%	15.6%	16.5%	5.4%	3.7%
3.3%		24.2%		31.4%		32.1%		9.0%	

Global M/F ratio:	M	F	M/F	Total
	3108	3144	0.988	6252

Population Under 5 yy of age (U5Y)

Pop M-F	M	F	Tot
All	3108	3144	6252
U5Y	844	876	1720
%	27.2%	27.9%	27.5%

PLW: (355) 5.7% Pregnant or Lactating Women

Perceived “Malnourished” (Undernourished): (93) 1.49%

The question was: “Do you think there is somebody undernourished in your house? Like too skinny or under-weight, or not growing enough?”

Perceived “Disabled” (with Diverse Ability): (49) 0.8%

The question was: “Do you think there is somebody with some impaired function in your house? Like not seeing well, or not earring, or not able to speak or to walk, and the like?”

3.1 Anthropometric results (based on WHO standards 2006):

- ✓ Global Acute Malnutrition or GAM is here defined as <-2 z scores weight-for-height and/or oedema and/or MUAC<125mm.
- ✓ Moderate Acute Malnutrition or MAM is here defined as <-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score, no oedema and/or MUAC<125 mm and >= 115 mm
- ✓ Severe Acute Malnutrition or SAM is here defined as <-3z scores weight-for-height and/or oedema and/or MUAC<115mm
- ✓ Exclusion of z-scores from Observed mean SMART flags: WHZ -3 to 3; HAZ -3 to 3; WAZ -3 to 3

Main survey results for WHZ:

Prevalence of global acute malnutrition (<-2 z-score and/or oedema)

All (1235): (109) **8.8%** (6.0-12.8 95% CI)
Boys (630): (67) 10.6% (7.2-15.4 95% CI)
Girls (605): (42) 6.9% (4.4-10.7 95% CI)

Prevalence of moderate acute malnutrition (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score, no oedema)

All (1235): (96) 7.8% (5.1-11.7 95% CI)
Boys (630): (57) 9.0% (5.9-13.7 95% CI)
Girls (605): (39) 6.4% (4.0-10.2 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe acute malnutrition (<-3 z-score and/or oedema)

All (1235): (13) **1.1%** (0.5- 2.2 95% CI)
Boys (630): (10) 1.6% (0.7- 3.6 95% CI)
Girls (605): (3) 0.5% (0.2- 1.5 95% CI)

% of oedema (n=9) : 0.7%
mean±SD of WHZ (n=1226) : -0.21±1.15
Design effect WHZ < -2 : 4.52
z-scores not available : 14
z-scores out of range : 32

95% CI: SUDAAN procedure for cluster and Wilson score interval for random sampling

Table 3.1: Distribution of age (in months) and sex of the nutrition sample

AGE (mo)	Boys		Girls		Total		Ratio
	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	Boy:girl
6-17	181	61.1	115	38.9	296	23.3	1.6
18-29	154	49.2	159	50.8	313	24.6	1.0
30-41	145	47.7	159	52.3	304	23.9	0.9
42-53	128	47.6	141	52.4	269	21.1	0.9
54-59	42	46.7	48	53.3	90	7.1	0.9
Total	650	51.1	622	48.9	1272	100.0	1.0

Table 3.2: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on weight-for-height z-scores (and/or oedema) and by sex

	All n = 1235	Boys n = 630	Girls n = 605
Prevalence of global malnutrition (<-2 z-score and/or oedema)	(109) 8.8 % (6.0 - 12.8 95% C.I.)	(67) 10.6 % (7.2 - 15.4 95% C.I.)	(42) 6.9 % (4.4 - 10.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate malnutrition (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score, no oedema)	(96) 7.8 % (5.1 - 11.7 95% C.I.)	(57) 9.0 % (5.9 - 13.7 95% C.I.)	(39) 6.4 % (4.0 - 10.2 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe malnutrition (<-3 z-score and/or oedema)	(13) 1.1 % (0.5 - 2.2 95% C.I.)	(10) 1.6 % (0.7 - 3.6 95% C.I.)	(3) 0.5 % (0.2 - 1.5 95% C.I.)

The prevalence of oedema is 0.7 %

Table 3.3: Prevalence of acute malnutrition by age, based on weight-for-height z-scores and/or oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (<-3 z-score)		Moderate wasting (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (>= -2 z score)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	285	1	0.4	38	13.3	243	85.3	3	1.1
18-29	298	2	0.7	24	8.1	267	89.6	5	1.7
30-41	295	0	0.0	23	7.8	271	91.9	1	0.3
42-53	267	0	0.0	9	3.4	258	96.6	0	0.0
54-59	90	1	1.1	2	2.2	87	96.7	0	0.0
Total	1235	4	0.3	96	7.8	1126	91.2	9	0.7

Table 3.4: Distribution of acute malnutrition and oedema based on weight-for-height z-scores

	<-3 z-score	>=-3 z-score
Oedema present	Marasmic kwashiorkor No. 1 (0.1 %)	Kwashiorkor No. 8 (0.6 %)
Oedema absent	Marasmic No. 18 (1.4 %)	Not severely malnourished No. 1240 (97.9 %)

Main survey results for MUAC:

Prevalence of global acute malnutrition

MUAC < 125 mm or edema

All (1268): (183) **14.4%** (11.8-17.5 95% CI)

Boys (647): (94) 14.5% (11.4-18.3 95% CI)

Girls (621): (89) 14.3% (11.0-18.5 95% CI)

Prevalence of moderate acute malnutrition

MUAC < 125 and MUAC >= 115 mm

All (1268): (140) 11.0% (8.7-13.9 95% CI)

Boys (647): (72) 11.1% (8.3-14.7 95% CI)

Girls (621): (68) 11.0% (8.1-14.7 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe acute malnutrition

MUAC < 115 mm or edema

All (1268): (43) **3.4%** (2.4- 4.7 95% CI)

Boys (647): (22) 3.4% (2.2- 5.3 95% CI)

Girls (621): (21) 3.4% (2.1- 5.3 95% CI)

% of oedema (n=9) : 0.7%

mean±SD of MUAC (n=1268) : 141.4±13.6

Design effect MUAC <125mm : 2.11

95% CI: SUDAAN procedure for cluster and Wilson score interval for random sampling

Table 3.5: Prevalence of acute malnutrition based on MUAC cut off's (and/or oedema) and by sex

	All n = 1268	Boys n = 647	Girls n = 621
Prevalence of global malnutrition (< 125 mm and/or oedema)	(183) 14.4 % (11.8 - 17.5 95% C.I.)	(94) 14.5 % (11.4 - 18.3 95% C.I.)	(89) 14.3 % (11.0 - 18.5 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate malnutrition (< 125 mm and >= 115 mm, no oedema)	(140) 11.0 % (8.7 - 13.9 95% C.I.)	(72) 11.1 % (8.3 - 14.7 95% C.I.)	(68) 11.0 % (8.1 - 14.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe malnutrition (< 115 mm and/or oedema)	(43) 3.4 % (2.4 - 4.7 95% C.I.)	(22) 3.4 % (2.2 - 5.3 95% C.I.)	(21) 3.4 % (2.1 - 5.3 95% C.I.)

Table 3.6: Prevalence of acute malnutrition by age, based on MUAC cut off's and/or oedema

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (< 115 mm)		Moderate wasting (>= 115 mm and < 125 mm)		Normal (>= 125 mm)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	296	20	6.8	79	26.7	197	66.6	3	1.0
18-29	312	8	2.6	40	12.8	264	84.6	5	1.6
30-41	302	2	0.7	14	4.6	286	94.7	1	0.3
42-53	268	4	1.5	5	1.9	259	96.6	0	0.0
54-59	90	1	1.1	3	3.3	86	95.6	0	0.0
Total	1268	35	2.8	141	11.1	1092	86.1	9	0.7

Table 3.7: Prevalence of underweight based on weight-for-age z-scores by sex

	All n = 1236	Boys n = 627	Girls n = 609
Prevalence of underweight (<-2 z-score)	(291) 23.5 % (19.9 - 27.7 95% C.I.)	(167) 26.6 % (22.4 - 31.4 95% C.I.)	(124) 20.4 % (16.0 - 25.5 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate underweight (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)	(208) 16.8 % (14.1 - 20.0 95% C.I.)	(122) 19.5 % (16.0 - 23.5 95% C.I.)	(86) 14.1 % (10.7 - 18.4 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe underweight (<-3 z-score)	(83) 6.7 % (5.2 - 8.6 95% C.I.)	(45) 7.2 % (5.0 - 10.1 95% C.I.)	(38) 6.2 % (4.4 - 8.7 95% C.I.)

Main survey results for WAZ:

Prevalence of underweight (<-2 z-score)

All (1236): (291) **23.5%** (19.9-27.7 95% CI)
Boys (627): (167) 26.6% (22.4-31.4 95% CI)
Girls (609): (124) 20.4% (16.0-25.5 95% CI)

Prevalence of moderate underweight (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)

All (1236): (208) 16.8% (14.1-20.0 95% CI)
Boys (627): (122) 19.5% (16.0-23.5 95% CI)
Girls (609): (86) 14.1% (10.7-18.4 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe underweight (<-3 z-score)

All (1236): (83) **6.7%** (5.2- 8.6 95% CI)
Boys (627): (45) 7.2% (5.0-10.1 95% CI)
Girls (609): (38) 6.2% (4.4- 8.7 95% CI)

% of oedema (n=9) : 0.7%
mean±SD of WAZ (n=1236) : -1.23±1.11
Design effect WAZ < -2 : 2.65
z-scores not available : 14
z-scores out of range : 22

95% CI: SUDAAN procedure for cluster and Wilson score interval for random sampling

Table 3.8: Prevalence of underweight by age, based on weight-for-age z-scores

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe underweight (<-3 z-score)		Moderate underweight (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	283	23	8.1	44	15.5	216	76.3	3	1.1
18-29	294	19	6.5	54	18.4	221	75.2	5	1.7
30-41	301	30	10.0	52	17.3	219	72.8	1	0.3
42-53	269	5	1.9	43	16.0	221	82.2	0	0.0
54-59	89	6	6.7	15	16.9	68	76.4	0	0.0
Total	1236	83	6.7	208	16.8	945	76.5	9	0.7

Table 3.9: Prevalence of stunting based on height-for-age z-scores and by sex

	All n = 1174	Boys n = 582	Girls n = 592
Prevalence of stunting (<-2 z-score)	(624) 53.2 % (49.6 - 56.6 95% C.I.)	(315) 54.1 % (50.0 - 58.2 95% C.I.)	(309) 52.2 % (46.8 - 57.6 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of moderate stunting (<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)	(357) 30.4 % (27.3 - 33.7 95% C.I.)	(174) 29.9 % (26.1 - 34.0 95% C.I.)	(183) 30.9 % (27.1 - 35.1 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe stunting (<-3 z-score)	(267) 22.7 % (19.5 - 26.3 95% C.I.)	(141) 24.2 % (20.6 - 28.3 95% C.I.)	(126) 21.3 % (17.1 - 26.2 95% C.I.)

Table 3.10: Prevalence of stunting by age based on height-for-age z-scores

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe stunting (<-3 z-score)		Moderate stunting (>= -3 and <-2 z-score)		Normal (> = -2 z score)	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	267	29	10.9	58	21.7	180	67.4
18-29	284	71	25.0	100	35.2	113	39.8
30-41	277	90	32.5	96	34.7	91	32.9
42-53	260	56	21.5	81	31.2	123	47.3
54-59	86	21	24.4	22	25.6	43	50.0
Total	1174	267	22.7	357	30.4	550	46.8

Main survey results for HAZ:

Prevalence of stunting
(<-2 z-score)

All (1174): (624) **53.2%** (49.6-56.6 95% CI)
Boys (582): (315) 54.1% (50.0-58.2 95% CI)
Girls (592): (309) 52.2% (46.8-57.6 95% CI)

Prevalence of moderate stunting
(<-2 z-score and >=-3 z-score)

All (1174): (357) 30.4% (27.3-33.7 95% CI)
Boys (582): (174) 29.9% (26.1-34.0 95% CI)
Girls (592): (183) 30.9% (27.1-35.1 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe stunting
(<-3 z-score)

All (1174): (267) **22.7%** (19.5-26.3 95% CI)
Boys (582): (141) 24.2% (20.6-28.3 95% CI)
Girls (592): (126) 21.3% (17.1-26.2 95% CI)

mean±SD of HAZ (n=1174) : -2.04±1.21

Design effect HAZ < -2 : 1.45

z-scores not available : 0

z-scores out of range : 98

95% CI: SUDAAN procedure for cluster and Wilson score interval for random sampling

Table 3.11: Prevalence of overweight based on weight for height cut off's and by sex (no oedema)

	All n = 1235	Boys n = 630	Girls n = 605
Prevalence of overweight (WHZ > 2)	(27) 2.2 % (1.4 - 3.3 95% C.I.)	(14) 2.2 % (1.3 - 3.9 95% C.I.)	(13) 2.1 % (1.2 - 3.7 95% C.I.)
Prevalence of severe overweight (WHZ > 3)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)	(0) 0.0 % (0.0 - 0.0 95% C.I.)

Table 3.12: Prevalence of overweight by age, based on weight for height (no oedema)

Age (mo)	Total no.	Overweight (WHZ > 2)		Severe Overweight (WHZ > 3)	
		No.	%	No.	%
6-17	285	4	1.4	0	0.0
18-29	298	6	2.0	0	0.0
30-41	295	5	1.7	0	0.0
42-53	267	10	3.7	0	0.0
54-59	90	2	2.2	0	0.0
Total	1235	27	2.2	0	0.0

Table 3.13: Mean z-scores, Design Effects and excluded subjects

Indicator	n	Mean z-scores \pm SD	Design Effect (z-score < -2)	z-scores not available*	z-scores out of range
Weight-for-Height	1226	-0.21 \pm 1.15	4.52	14	32
Weight-for-Age	1236	-1.23 \pm 1.11	2.65	14	22
Height-for-Age	1174	-2.04 \pm 1.21	1.45	0	98

* contains for WHZ and WAZ the children with edema.

Combined Acute Malnutrition

Calculated according to the following criteria:

GAM: MUAC<125mm	and/or oedema	and/or WHZ <-2 Zs
MAM: 115mm>MUAC<125mm	no oedema	and/or -3 Zs ≥ WHZ ≤ -2 Zs
SAM: MUAC<115mm	and/or oedema	and/or WHZ<-3 Zs

The concepts being:

- a) whatever the criteria for the diagnosis of Acute Malnutrition, MUAC, WHZ or oedema, it is sufficient to formulate the diagnosis
- b) for the diagnosis of MAM it is necessary a MUAC between 115 and 125mm and/or a WHZ between -3 and -2 Z scores and no oedema must be present
- c) for the diagnosis of SAM it is necessary a MUAC lower than 115mm and/or oedema and/or a WHZ < -3 Z scores

To calculate these quantities in consideration of the WHO 2006 standards and with SMART flags applied (as we did for all data) we operated as follows:

1) Define:

GAMm	= GAM according to MUAC and/or oedema
GAMz	= GAM according to WHZ
GAMb	= GAM according to the presence of <u>both</u> previous criteria
MAMm	= MAM according to MUAC and/or oedema
MAMz	= MAM according to WHZ
MAMb	= MAM according to the presence of <u>both</u> previous criteria
SAMm	= SAM according to MUAC and/or oedema
SAMz	= SAM according to WHZ
SAMb =	= SAM according to the presence of <u>both</u> previous criteria

2) Then:

$$GAMc = GAMm + GAMz - GAMb$$

and in more detail:

GAMc = GAM combined = GAMm + GAMz – GAMb

MAMc = MAM combined = MAMm + MAMz - MAMb

SAMc = SAM combined = SAMm + SAMz – SAMb

- 3) Create new categorical variables GAMb MAMb SAMb as categorical variables y/n
- 4) Extract Excel spreadsheet from ENA and apply logic formulas at column level as:
 - IF (MUAC<125) AND (WHZ<-2) = identifies GAMb
 - IF ((MUAC<115) OR (edema y)) AND (WHZ< -3) = identifies SAMb
 - Then apply COUNTIF to obtain # GAMb and SAMb (MAMb = GAMb-SAMb)
- 5) Calculate # GAMc MAMc SAMc according to (***) distinguished by sex, according to WHO 2006 tables with SMART flags applied
- 6) Create the following table:

Multiple Criteria Acute Malnutrition				
children 6-59mths				
		All	M	F
GAMm	MUAC <125 or oedema	183	94	89
		14.4%	14.5%	14.3%
MAMm	MUAC 125-115 no oedema	140	72	68
		11.0%	11.1%	11.0%
SAMm	MUAC <115 or oedema	43	22	21
		3.4%	3.4%	3.4%
<hr/>				
GAMz	WHZ <-2 or oedema	109	67	42
		8.8%	10.6%	6.9%
MAMz	WHZ -2 to -3 no oedema	96	57	39
		7.8%	9.0%	6.4%
SAMz	WHZ <-3 or oedema	13	10	3
		1.1%	1.6%	0.5%
<hr/>				
GAMb	both criteria GAM	83	48	35
		5.8%	6.7%	4.8%
MAMb	both criteria MAM	70	39	31
		4.9%	5.4%	4.3%
SAMb	both criteria SAM	13	9	4
		0.9%	1.3%	0.6%
<hr/>				
GAMc	combined criteria GAM	209	113	96
		16.5%	17.5%	15.5%
MAMc	combined criteria MAM	166	90	76
		13.1%	13.9%	12.2%
SAMc	combined criteria SAM	43	23	20
		3.4%	3.6%	3.4%

NB: to be noticed that this is a more conservative approach, i.e. taking into account SMART flags exclusions; removing the SMART flags prevalence can be higher.

- 7) Finally, on the AMc AM-combined prevalence a CI⁹⁵ is calculated according to the CLT *Central Limit Theorem*⁶ formula. Taking into consideration WHO 2006 table, SMART flags applied, the final result is:

combined criteria malnutrition(*)	All (1268)	Boys (647)	Girls (621)
Combined GAMc and CI95 ¹	16.5 (n=209) 14.4 - 18.5 %	17.5 (n=113) 14.6 - 20.4 %	15.5 (n=96) 12.7 - 18.3 %
Combined MAMc and CI95 ¹	13.1 (n=166) 11.2 - 14.9%	13.9 (n=90) 11.2 - 16.6%	12.2 (n=76) 9.6 - 14.8%
Combined SAMc and CI95 ¹	3.4 (n=43) 2.4 - 4.4 %	3.6 (n=23) 2.2 - 5.0 %	3.4 (n=20) 2.0 - 4.8 %

N*: Calculation according to internal software and **CLT formula**

We are aware that this distribution can be not-Gaussian and that there can be other methods to calculate combined Acute Malnutrition and related Confidence Interval.

E.g. for control we recalculated CI95 on combined AM by “*Wilson Score Interval*” and the outcomes are as follows:

combined criteria malnutrition(**)	All (1268)	Boys (647)	Girls (621)
Combined GAMc and CI95 ¹	16.5 (n=209) 14.5 - 18.6 %	17.5 (n=113) 14.7 - 20.6 %	15.5 (n=96) 12.8 - 18.5 %
Combined MAMc and CI95 ¹	13.1 (n=166) 11.4 - 15.1%	13.9 (n=90) 11.5 - 16.8%	12.2 (n=76) 9.9 - 15.0%
Combined SAMc and CI95 ¹	3.4 (n=43) 2.5 - 4.5 %	3.6 (n=23) 2.4 - 5.3 %	3.4 (n=20) 2.1 - 4.9 %

N*: Calculation online using the **Wilson Score Interval formula for proportions**

In all cases it is our opinion, in accord to what ACF stated in their recent Ghor Province SMART Assessment⁷, that the combined Acute Malnutrition prevalence shall be the best indicator for program design and caseload calculation.

We do hope that in future ENA software releases these calculations will be added to that already powerful software.

⁶ Newcombe, Robert G. "Two-Sided Confidence Intervals for the Single Proportion: Comparison of Seven Methods," *Statistics in Medicine*, **17**, 857-872 (1998).

We used, for CI-95%; with p = decimal percentage, n = number observations (>30) and Za = 1.96

$$I = \left(\hat{p} - z_{\alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n-1}}, \hat{p} + z_{\alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n-1}} \right)$$

⁷ ACF Afghanistan, Nutrition & Mortality SMART survey final report, 16 August to 4 September, 2016.

3.2 Mortality & Natality results (retrospective over 120 days prior to interview)

Calculation CDR done according SMART formula

$$\text{population at risk} = \text{pop} + d/2 + l/2 - j/2 - b/2$$

$$\text{days of risk} = \text{recall}$$

$$\text{CDR} = (\text{deaths} * 10,000) / (\text{pop at risk} / \text{recall}) \quad [n/10k/day]$$

Recall period = 120 days, from Eid ul Adha (Sept 11 2016)⁸

index	score	Unit	CI95	Design Effect
CMR	0.96	/ 10,000 people/day	0.72 – 1.29	DEFF 1.48
U5MR	1.12	/ 10,000 children under 5 / day	0.64 – 1.94	DEFF 1.62

As calculated by ENA 2011, Household level data-entry

Mortality: numbers, distinguishing Male / Female with segregated Under 5 Y

As calculated from our internal database, it gives largely analogous results:

Deaths #	M	F	All
Adults	34	16	50
U5Y	10	12	22
All	44	28	72
CDR	1.18	0.74	0.96
CDR<5	0.99	1.14	1.07

To be noticed that the number of adults' male deaths is more than double compared to the females. The different is nearly completely due to higher number of violent deaths.

Causes of death:

Unknown
18.1%
Injury or Trauma
26.4%
Illness
55.6%

Violent deaths (Injury or Trauma): (n tot = 19)

adult males (>18y) = 11 adult females (>18y) = 2 total adults (>18) = 13

children and boys <18 = 5 girls (<18) = 1 total <18 = 6

⁸ Here we had to face a complication due to different recall period of Phase 1(111 days) compared to Phase 2 (142 days) the intermediate value being 128 days. But considering the higher number of people assessed in Phase 1 we shifted proportionally the overall recall period to 120 days (see calculation on page19).

Location of death:

Current
84.7%
During Migration
2.8%
Previous Location
9.7%
Other
2.8%

Of the violent deaths:

1 occurred during migration: a male baby 35 months old of an IDP family now in Eid Gaah village of Zhari district

2 occurred in previous location: two babies, twins (one male and one female) 8 months old, now in Zakar Sharef village of Kandahar (Dand) district

All the others violent deaths occurred in current location

Birth Crude Rate: BCR 1.96 / 10,000 / day

N: For comparison purposes we report also the Mortality rates as calculated for the Phase 1 alone (recall 111 days)

Index	score	Unit	CI95	Design Effect
CMR	0.79	/ 10,000 people/day	0.53 – 1.18	DEFF 1.35
U5MR	1.10	/ 10,000 children under 5 / day	0.53 – 2.28	DEFF 1.74

4. Food Security

Household Dietary Diversity Score HDDS = 4.3 ± 2.0 (M±SD); Median 4

Measure diversity of nutrients in the diet based on 12 food groups (see appendix)

Single Score = sum of n food groups eaten yesterday; range 0-12

Population Score = sum of all HDDS / n households (= average)

Ranges: 0-4 poor; 5-8 acceptable; 9-12 good

So our results is near to “poor diversity” range

Food Consumption Score FCS = 50.5 ± 32.1 (M±SD); Median 48 FCS < 35: 17.1%

Measure quantity and quality of consummated food based on 9 food groups (A, B, ...I)

Nutritional value index (i) for each food group; n = number of days eaten last week

Single Score = Ani + Bni + ... Ini; range 0 – 129.5

Population Score = sum of all FCSS / n households (= average)

<21 = poor; 21-35 = borderline; > 35 = good

So our result has an average in the middle range, but with a high standard deviation, meaning that there are important differences within different households. So we follow another approach using the threshold of FCS 35 to find that 17.1% of the sample does not reach the sufficient food consumption score of 35.

Variety 1 = Variety of primary sources of food

Variety 2 = Variety of secondary sources of food

This measures how many different sources of foods (whatever the type of food) are available for the family (for different kind of sources see list in the appendix)

Sources	Var 1	Var 2
1 source	31.0%	15.5%
2 sources	49.2%	6.3%
3 ,,,	10.7%	0.6%
4 ,,,	5.2%	0.2%
5 ,,,	0.8%	0.0%

Interpretation:

31.0% of the families have only one kind of primary source of food

49.2% ,, have two different kind of primary sources of food

15.5% of the families have only one secondary source of food

Double sources = 34.1% percentage of household who have at least a double (= at least one alternative) source for the single specific kind/class of food. (Contrary to the “varieties” this refer to the single specific kind/class of food, to check if there are at least two different sources for that specific kind/class of food).

So taken together these results show a mid level dependence of the community from different sources of food: disaggregating the results we have also seen an higher dependence in urban (tendency to single source market) than in rural (tendency to double sources market + auto-production)

Household Hunger Score HHS = 8.1 ± 5.3 (M±SD); Median 8

Sequence of 9 “missing food” questions: score for single question are 0-3

Index of Hunger of the Household; Range from 0 (no hunger) to 27 (famine)

Our result shows a tendency to low hunger (or low awareness) of shortage of food and food insecurity within the community.

5. WASH

Water source > 500 m from home: W>500m: 18.1%

Distance over 500m is generally considered equivalent to NO-access to water.

Kind of water source:

Stream 6.7%, River 0.2%, Spring 9.5%, Well with hand operated pump 60.9%, Well with electric motor pump with tampon batteries and solar panel 18.8%, Tap water 0.0%

Stream
6.7%
River
0.2%
Spring
9.5%
Well handp
60.9%
Well motorp
18.8%
Tap W
0.0%

Latrines type:

- ✓ “open type” (no latrine) 33.7%;
- ✓ “rural type” (common type in use in the area, roofed, mud construction, not always differentiated female/male, not always illuminated, generally one latrine per 1 to 2 households (12 to 24 people), generally within 25 meters from home
- ✓ “sewage system” (inside the house with collection system and septic tank “Imhoff-like”)

Open
33.7%
Rural
59.1%
Sewage
2.6%

Hand washing practices:

Water and soap in 24.4% of cases, a small percentage 0.6% claim cannot practically wash hands because of scarcity of water

Cannot
0.6%
Sand
0.0%
Ashes
1.0%
Water
69.8%
W & Soap
24.4%

Hand washing timing:

Morning and evening: 25.2%; before eating 13.7%; before preparing the food for the family 4.6% (aa: 96% of respondents were women performing cooking for the family); after defecation 2.8%; mixed response including “before preparation of food” 16.3%; mixed response not including “before preparation of food” 33.7%; in all the cases 0%.

Mrn/Eve	25.2%
Before Eat	13.7%
Before Food	4.6%
After Feces	2.8%
Mix w3	16.3%
Mix no3	33.7%
All	0.0%

We considered more critical the hand washing practice before preparation of food. This is accomplished in $4.6+16.3 = 20.9\%$ of cases.

Drinking water treatment/practices:

No treatment (just spontaneous sedimentation): 96.0%; filtering: 0%; use of chlorine based or similar chemical disinfectants 0.2; boiling water 0.4%; buying drinking water bottles 0%

Nothing	96.0%
Filtering	0.0%
Chlorine	0.2%
Boil	0.4%
Buy	0.0%

6. Breastfeeding and Vaccinations

Breastfeeding mixed with other ailments in the first 6 months of life = 73.2%

Breastfeeding started within one hour from birth = 48.2%

Perceived Vaccination Coverage of the family:

The question was: “As far as you know have all the family members received their full vaccination coverage?”

All
15.3%
Not Sure
15.5%
Not All
58.1%
Nobody
6.3%

Vaccination booklet(s) in concordance with what the respondent said: 23.8%

The enumerators checked: a) if vaccination booklet(s) was/were available b) if what was documented in the booklet(s) was in accord to what was told by the responders.

7. Problems

Main problems encountered during the survey have been:

- Security: in phase 2 some team had to avoid dangerous roads (filled with IEDs!) and to do so had to resort to specialized local advice.
- Around 85% of the respondents cannot identify the exact birthday of the child even with the aid of local calendar: Pashtun calendar, Dari Calendar, Gregorian calendar mixing up with lack of documents contribute to this limitation. Best acceptable identification was based on age in months.
- Identification of the villages: many villages have more than one name depending on some notable local stakeholder mullah or commander and can be named in one way or the other depending on the personal view of the respondent; this of course complicate navigation in the absence of any geographic identification of the locality at field level.
- Numerals data entry: Pashtun language (the language of the questionnaires!) is written right to left and sometime some enumerator sporadically (wrongly!) entered digits in reverse (i.e. cm 91.7 becoming a 19.7, which can be easily spotted, but a cm 56.4 to 65.4 high will be less promptly apparent instead!). And one more is upon the numeral “0” which is a dot “ . “ in Pashtun numerals

8. Data Quality Discussion and Analysis

8.a Quality of data

ENA software gives a in-plausibility score of **13/100 = “good”** to the SMART part of this assessment, the threshold of “problematic” being 25/100(see appendix).

The overall quality of WHZ data is good to excellent regarding Flagged data, Overall sex ratio, Age ratio and Digit preference score. However there is a tendency to negative Skewness and Kurtosis and a clearly Significant Poisson distribution for WHZ -2. The SD of the WHZ was also progressively increasing with the increase of data amount incoming from city distant clusters during the survey. This was something we considered interesting and possibly linked not only to bias but also to clear dis-homogeneity within the sample. Final WHZ SD is 1.15. More on this will be elaborated on the analysis.

Many anthropometries are flagged for possible wrong age. We also found difficult to impossible to identify exact birthday in a lot of households. Age in months has then been used for the majority of anthropometries. There is also a clear tendency by enumerators to round up the age in months based on the known age in years of the child (12-24-36 etc.) Also as consequence of these limitations HAZ (but not WAZ) SD is out of the limit, reaching 1.21 (WAZ SD 1.11)

There is also a tendency to digit preference for the numerals 2 and 4. We presumed this to be dependent to some possible confusion between Western versus Oriental Hindi-Arabic and Pashtun numerals. In some occasion numbers have been (wrongly!) written on the questionnaires in reverse direction (i.e. e.g. 25.7 for 52.7) generally easily detected (19.3 for 91.3) but in some case more difficult to ascertain (e.g. 56.5 for 65.5).

As a whole we considered the data quality as good but with a tendency to dis-homogeneity within the sample, increasing as the teams were moving toward the more remote clusters.

8.b Discussion

The data demonstrate a dire **Malnutrition** situation both Acute as well as Chronic which by all standards can be classified between serious and emergency level (**GAM >15% and SAM >3% when calculated as combined prevalence.**

Our data are similar to the ones obtained by other NGOs in similar Afghan Provinces (ACF SMART surveys in Ghor, Kapisa and Nangarhar, 2016). It must be pointed out that there may be different method to calculate the combined GAM SAM prevalence and CI95 and we used one of the more conservative one.

The higher Acute Malnutrition prevalence is the one obtained calculating the combined indicators (GAMc 16.5, SAMc 3.4%) Then follows the one calculated by MUAC (GAMm 14.4, SAMm 3.4%) then WHZ (GAMz 8.8., SAMz 1.1) and last is the prevalence based on both MUAC and WHZ criteria (GAMb 5.8, SAMb 0.9%).

The number of children satisfying both criteria WHZ and MUAC for GAM and/or for SAM is less than the other two: in our sample (according to WHO 2006 standards and with SMART flags applied) we found:

183 children GAMm according to MUAC <125mm (43 SAM, <115 or oedema)

109 children GAMz according to WHZ <-2 (13 SAMz <-3 WHZ)

83 children GAMz according to both MUAC and to WHZ (13 SAMb)

Then as: $183+109-83= 209$ and $43+13-13 = 43$

It results in 209 GAMc (i.e. prevalence 16.5% in our sample) and 43 SAMc (i.e. prevalence 3.4%) of children affected by “combined General and - respectively - Severe Acute Malnutrition”

We constantly found a **higher prevalence of Acute Malnutrition in boys** compared to girls. Such difference is very **evident in the WHZ based acute malnutrition (GAMz)**.

Prevalence of global acute malnutrition (<-2 z-score and/or oedema)

All (1235): (109) **8.8%** (6.0-12.8 95% CI)

Boys (630): (67) **10.6%** (7.2-15.4 95% CI)

Girls (605): (42) **6.9%** (4.4-10.7 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe acute malnutrition (<-3 z-score and/or oedema)

All (1235): (13) **1.1%** (0.5- 2.2 95% CI)

Boys (630): (10) **1.6%** (0.7- 3.6 95% CI)

Girls (605): (3) **0.5%** (0.2- 1.5 95% CI)

Similar results have been observed by other organizations performing SMART surveys in Afghanistan (ACF AIM-WG presentation of the survey in Farah province, March 2017).

The reason for this difference is unknown but we do suspect that it cannot be linked to some primarily biologic motivation. Some cultural / behavioral man-induced practice can be in place and as: (i) the male child is generally the object of greater attentions and care compared to the female, for cultural reasons, in rural Afghanistan, but (ii) those attentions and care are sometime (not rarely) incorrect (see the 73.2% prevailing idea that breastfeeding mixed with other nutrients is good in the first 6 months of life) so the increased GAMz and SAMz observed in boys can be the consequence of incorrect practices.

This difference however it is NOT present when one goes to compare boys and girls in relation to MUAC-based Acute Malnutrition (what we call GAMm)

Prevalence of global acute malnutrition
MUAC < 125 mm or edema

All (1268): (183) **14.4%** (11.8-17.5 95% CI)
Boys (647): (94) **14.5%** (11.4-18.3 95% CI)
Girls (621): (89) **14.3%** (11.0-18.5 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe acute malnutrition
MUAC < 115 mm or edema

All (1268): (43) **3.4%** (2.4- 4.7 95% CI)
Boys (647): (22) **3.4%** (2.2- 5.3 95% CI)
Girls (621): (21) **3.4%** (2.1- 5.3 95% CI)

Which can be another point in favour of the idea that MUAC based and WHZ based malnutrition are dependent on more or less slightly different underlying patterns.

Of course the relevant difference between male and females in GAMz-SAMz acute malnutrition prevalence is reflected also in the combined GAMc-SAMc.

	All	Male	Female
Combined GAMc and CI95 ¹	16.5 (n=209) 14.4 - 18.5 %	17.5 (n=113) 14.6 - 20.4 %	15.5 (n=96) 12.7 - 18.3 %
Combined MAMc and CI95 ¹	13.1 (n=166) 11.2 - 14.9%	13.9 (n=90) 11.2 - 16.6%	12.2 (n=76) 9.6 - 14.8%
Combined SAMc and CI95 ¹	3.4 (n=43) 2.4 - 4.4 %	3.6 (n=23) 2.2 - 5.0 %	3.4 (n=20) 2.0 - 4.8 %

However this difference tends to be reduced in Chronic Malnutrition, were the two sexes have more similar prevalence in **Underweight**.

Prevalence of underweight (<-2 z-score)
All (1236): (291) **23.5%** (19.9-27.7 95% CI)
Boys (627): (167) **26.6%** (22.4-31.4 95% CI)
Girls (609): (124) **20.4%** (16.0-25.5 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe underweight (<-3 z-score)
All (1236): (83) **6.7%** (5.2- 8.6 95% CI)
Boys (627): (45) **7.2%** (5.0-10.1 95% CI)
Girls (609): (38) **6.2%** (4.4- 8.7 95% CI)

This tendency to equalize is even more clear in **Stunting** were the two prevalence rates are nearing the same.

Prevalence of stunting (<-2 z-score)

All (1174): (624) **53.2%** (49.6-56.6 95% CI)
Boys (582): (315) **54.1%** (50.0-58.2 95% CI)
Girls (592): (309) **52.2%** (46.8-57.6 95% CI)

Prevalence of severe stunting (<-3 z-score)

All (1174): (267) **22.7%** (19.5-26.3 95% CI)
Boys (582): (141) **24.2%** (20.6-28.3 95% CI)
Girls (592): (126) **21.3%** (17.1-26.2 95% CI)

Similar results have been obtained by ACF in their recent Ghor SMART survey, August 2016.

As we stated, the reasons for these differences are unknown, however, being no foreseeable biological reason, we do suspect that to be the consequence of cultural derived practices and specifically the result of the greater attention and cure which as rule of thumb are given more to the male compared to the female babies in rural Afghanistan. Being sometime some of those “cures” wrong – (we think to mixed breastfeeding) – the consequences can be bad for the “cured”. This can also explain why in later stages the tendency reduces - or even inverts - with similar or greater prevalence of chronically malnourished girls than boys. We would like to investigate on the matter with further studies.

It shall be also noticed that as for our knowledge the data from Health facilities shows frequently an inverse pattern with more girls acceding the nutrition services than boys.

Another tendency we observed in the sample is related to the age in months.

The **prevalence of Acute Malnutrition** both General as well as Severe (here showed the MUAC dependent GAMm-SAMm) is age dependent in inverse relationship and it **reduces with the increase of the age** of the child.

Age (mo)	Total no.	Severe wasting (< 115 mm)		Moderate wasting (>= 115 mm and < 125 mm)		Normal (> = 125 mm)		Oedema	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
6-17	296	20	6.8	79	26.7	197	66.6	3	1.0
18-29	312	8	2.6	40	12.8	264	84.6	5	1.6
30-41	302	2	0.7	14	4.6	286	94.7	1	0.3
42-53	268	4	1.5	5	1.9	259	96.6	0	0.0
54-59	90	1	1.1	3	3.3	86	95.6	0	0.0
Total	1268	35	2.8	141	11.1	1092	86.1	9	0.7

This is reasonable as the susceptibility of the body to malnutrition is greater in the early stages of life and then reduces gradually as growth naturally slows progressively

Interestingly, there is a little prevalence of moderate obesity WHZ >2 Z score 2.2%, which is concentrated in urban clusters as we will discuss further later.

The severe obesity WHZ > +3 is absent: 0.0%

Mortality is higher than expected and higher compared to previous assessments in the area reaching 0.96/10,000/day in adults and 1.12/10,000/day in the under 5 years of age.

Adult mortality rate is higher in males compared to females in adulthood whilst similar in the two sexes in the under 5 years of age.

We registered a total of 72 deaths within the recall period and actually the number of adult's male deaths (34) is more than double than the one of female's (16).

The assessment did not include full verbal autopsies but the general question about the illness/senility versus trauma/injury cause of death (plus the "unknown cause") was present. It came out with a relevant percentage of trauma related deaths (26.4%) demonstrating that the male/female difference is motivated by the greater number of trauma-related deaths in males. Of the recorded 19 "violent deaths" (for Injury or Trauma) 3 are of females and 16 are of males (11 adults and 5 children and boys <18yy)

To be observed that the **Birth Crude Rate** (1.96/10,000/ day) is more than double the Crude Death Rate.

Descriptive statistics of our sample of 504 households, 6252 persons, depict a very peculiar situation of Afghanistan resulting from a continuous "Longest War" condition of 40 years of armed conflict.

"Household" average persons is as high as 12.4 meaning an average of two "families" are living under the same roof and eating from the same pot (average family in Kandahar province 6.8 according to NSP database).

Given the **very high birth rate** it is a lower surprise to find a percentage of under 5 years of age as high as 27.5%

The respondents to the questionnaire are female in 96.0% of cases but the head of family is a man in 90.9% of the households. Which in turn, given the known structure of the Afghan family, can also indicate a derivate index of $(100 - 90.9) = 9.1\%$ **of women as "heads of family"** including a probable relevant component of widows considering the number of men killed during the enduring civil war.

Very interesting is in our opinion the **very low awareness of Malnutrition in the society**: only 1.5% answered "yes" to the question regarding the presence of some malnourished individual in their household. This prevalence is 10 times lower than the measured Acute Malnutrition and 30 to 40 times lower than the measured prevalence of Underweight or Stunting in the 6-59 months age group. **It is clear that the family will not look for help from the nutritional services if they do not perceive malnourished the child, or the PLW, or the young man or women whatever**, as malnutrition does affect the whole society and not only the early ages of life.

Due to the original "Rapid" nature of our assessment we do not measured the MUAC of PLW as we considered the classical 6-59 months sector the relevant proxy to show the prevalence of malnutrition in the whole population. Given the situation we can quite safely assume that an important percentage of young men, women and mothers is malnourished already and in need of help and supplementary diet in terms of calories, quality of food, micronutrients and vitamins.

The **Food Security indicators show a situation of middle to low food scarcity and insecurity**. The dietary indexes show a low diversity (HDDS median 4 over a 0-12 scale) and the quantity and nutritive quality of consummated food is middle to low (FCS median 48 over a 0-129.5 scale). However the hunger index is also low (HHS median 8 over a 0 to 27 range) indicating also here a **low awareness of the household toward the unsatisfying dietary conditions**.

However, the Standard Deviation of these indexes is comparatively very high, indicating high dispersion in the sample. Following a different approach we calculated the percentage of households living on an FCS <35, conventionally considered the limit for an acceptable diet, finding that **17.1% of the households are living at a FCS lower than 35**. This prevalence is comparable to the Acute Malnutrition prevalence and suggests that beside low awareness also the scarcity of quality and quantity of food can be probably a relevant factor in the malnutrition found in the province.

The secure availability of food is at mid level, also due to the fact that only **35.4% of the households can gather the single type of food from two different sources**. The more frequent primary and secondary sources of food being bazar purchase and own production.

WASH indicators are also unsatisfying as **18.1% of the sample has access to water at a distance > 500 m from home** (considered equivalent to no access). The majority of people in the sample get water from well served by hand-operates pump (60.9%). The percentage of **people not using the latrines** (because lack of latrines or for other reasons, this is not specified) is a **worrying 33.7%**. Only in a minority of households **hands are washed with soap (24.4%)** and again a minority **wash hands before preparing food for the family (20.9%)**.

Breastfeeding mixed with solid ailments is still considered a correct practice by 73.2% of the surveyed HHs. This is a higher prevalence compared to the one normally found in other surveys, which may depend on the way the question was raised, i.e. in a "positive" way (the question was: "*In the first six months of life do you feed the baby with other ailments beside breast milk?*"). Less than half of the mothers (**48.2%**) **consider important to start breastfeeding within the first hour** of life.

Vaccination coverage relevance shall not be clear for the households as **6.3% of the respondents declared never to have done any kind of vaccination** in the family (we had at time of the assessment - February 3 2017 - a new case of poliomyelitis in Kandahar city). The majority of households (58.1%) has done some vaccination but not completed all the cycles. **Only 22.0% of the households can demonstrate a vaccination booklet with complete information in accordance to what they verbally reported**.

Finally, from these data (Awareness of Malnutrition and Food Security, WASH and Breastfeeding practices, Vaccination's relevance knowledge) it is possible to indirectly infer that also the **general health awareness and health education level in the province is insufficient**, and this of course can be another important factor to be considered in comprehensive projects.

8c. Data analysis

As mentioned we found a progressive increase in WHZ SD, DEFF, modification of the Skewness, Kurtosis and arousal of a Significance of the Poisson distribution for WHZ -2 with the progression of the assessment toward the farer clusters.

The tendency of the distribution curve of WHZ to show an increasingly evident bi-modal pattern may not be so clear when WHZ Gaussian diagram is plotted using NCHS 1977 reference.

But become apparent when to be applied are references WHO 2006

Kandahar MSRA-SMART January 2017 (INTERSOS-HRDA)

And it is interesting to note that a similar curve has been detected by ACF in their recent Ghor SMART survey

Ghor SMART August 2016 (ACF)

Doing assessment with Provincial coverage in Afghanistan it is to be expected that, with the increase of the size of the sample, it will generally become more apparent the dis-homogeneity within the assessed population. This is to mean that of course the conditions in Kandahar city, Dand district, are very different if compared to the ones that can be encountered in a remote village.

So to better understand the underlying conditions of the population we started to segregate and compare data.

The first disaggregation was of the **Urban vs Rural population**. We studied the WHZ distribution to find that based on WHZ the **Acute GAMz Malnutrition average is low in Urban Kandahar** (WHZ mean +0.27 SD 1.02; n= 126)

Apart a small prevalence 2.4% of overweight (!) children⁹

⁹ But the high CI95 due to the small number of cases (0.4 12.9) does not allow any further conclusion. There may be, and actually there are, according to MEDAIR reports) pockets of high malnutrition even in the urban territory).

While there is a an average **7.7% (5.2 – 11.3 CI95) GAMz prevalence in Rural**;
(WHZ mean – 0.20; SD 1.15; n = 1103; DEFF WHZ < -2 = 3.54)

The second disaggregation we did was of **Resident versus Non-Resident (IDP+ Returnees Documented or Undocumented)** population

Based on WHZ there is **5.8% (3.9 – 8.5 CI95) General Acute Malnutrition in Residents**
(WHZ mean – 0.08; SD 1.10; n= 992; DEFF WHZ < -2 = 2.43)

Versus a **13.0% (7.7 – 21.3 CI95) prevalence of GAMz in Non-Residents**
(WHZ mean -0.52; SD 1.21; n= 230; DEFF WHZ <- 2 = 2.09)

It is beyond the scope of the present assessment to further explore with more sophisticated statistical tests as variance analysis or linear regression but with these data we could affirm with some confidence that the **Malnutrition is worst in Rural area and in Non Residents (mainly IDP, as the number of Documented and Undocumented Returnees is too small to make some conclusion) population** if compared to the Urban areas and the Resident population.

Plotting the **distribution of WHZ in Clusters**, it is obtained the following:

Showing a clear difference between “better” and “worst” clusters/villages in our sample.

In conclusion, from the amount of available data it is apparent the dis homogeneity within the sample, with presence of “pockets” of higher malnutrition. Those pockets seems to be associated with rural characteristic of the cluster, higher prevalence of non-resident (especially IDP), and as well with other indicators like higher mortality, lower health education and worst WASH and FS conditions.

We therefore tried to identify these “pockets” of higher suffering and unattended needs.

To do so we cross-tabulated the cluster lists with associated WHZ and MUAC averages and SD. We added for each cluster the known population figures and the number of identified “combined General Acute Malnutrition” (GAMc) children as well as their status as residents or non-residents.

With the aid of software it is then easy to rank the cluster (e.g. from “worst” to best”) according to the different parameters. As expected, the rank based on MUAC’s averages gives similar, but NOT identical ranking compared to the one based on WHZ’s averages. In all cases, with this method and with the visual aid of priority color codes (dark red, red, orange, yellow in decreasing order of priority) we identified again the association of malnutrition with the number of non-residents,

Then, in the search of a unified parameter, we came out with a comprehensive index including the number of “combined acutely malnourished” plus the number of non-residents in relation to the cluster population. We called this Ki (Comprehensive Index)

$$Ki = [(\# GAMc + \# Non-Residents) \times 100] / \# cluster population$$

And we ranked that index to obtain the “cluster priority table” in the next pages.

Finally, with the aim to obtain a map of the major needs (at least in terms of nutrition) at provincial level, we grouped the data of the “cluster priority table” at district level. This is done because the planning of humanitarian interventions to fight malnutrition and improve health (at least at NGO level) it is generally done on districts’ unit. In this way we obtained the following list:

District	Kd-Index	
Maywand	161.10%	
Nesh	116.80%	
Reg	113.30%	
Zhari	86.50%	
Daman	62.40%	
Maruf	56.60%	
Shaga	54.00%	
Shawalikot	53.00%	
Panjwayi	48.70%	
Spin Boldak	32.80%	
Arghistan	23.10%	
Khakriz	18.20%	
Miya Nishin	13.10%	
Arghandab	11.60%	
Kandahar	10.90%	

Cluster	PD/R	District	Village	Population	M-MUAC	MUAC M ± SD	M-WHZ	Weight-for-Height z-scores ± SD	GAMc	No-Resid	Kv-index
215	R	Maruf	Landai	496	137.9	Cluster 215 : 137.90 ±14.01 (n=17)	0.03	Cluster 215 : 0.03 ± 0.83 (n=17)	7	11	362.9%
19	R	Maywand	Klan kicha	656	135.3	Cluster 19 : 135.30 ±12.00 (n=14)	-0.49	Cluster 19 : -0.49 ± 1.42 (n=14)	7	10	259.1%
9	R	Daman	Zaker Abad kalai	1056	131.2	Cluster 9 : 131.20 ± 8.26 (n=21)	-1.66	Cluster 9 : -1.66 ± 1.22 (n=21)	18	8	246.2%
22	R	Maywand	Dazhari walaswali kali	770	133.0	Cluster 22 : 133.00 ±12.01 (n=17)	-1.61	Cluster 22 : -1.61 ± 0.95 (n=17)	11	6	220.8%
18	R	Maywand	Kariz Wal	1050	129.5	Cluster 18 : 129.50 ±16.49 (n=13)	-0.31	Cluster 18 : -0.31 ± 1.45 (n=12)	10	13	219.0%
20	R	Maywand	Hayatullah kalai	1011	140.1	Cluster 20 : 140.10 ±15.08 (n=15)	-1.53	Cluster 20 : -1.53 ± 1.13 (n=14)	12	6	178.0%
217	R	Maruf	Koli	1820	128.1	Cluster 217 : 128.10 ±12.21 (n=17)	-0.74	Cluster 217 : -0.74 ± 0.94 (n=17)	12	17	159.3%
223	R	Nesh	Sardagh	1427	136.6	Cluster 223 : 136.60 ± 5.88 (n=8)	-1.92	Cluster 223 : -1.92 ± 0.13 (n=8)	11	11	154.2%
49	R	Zhari	Sartak	1174	138.6	Cluster 49 : 138.60 ±12.81 (n=20)	-0.90	Cluster 49 : -0.90 ± 1.02 (n=19)	5	13	153.3%
213	R	Maruf	Abtoo Bahlolzai	595	133.8	Cluster 213 : 133.80 ±14.65 (n=15)	-1.04	Cluster 213 : -1.04 ± 1.10 (n=15)	9	0	151.3%
48	R	Zhari	Sahidano kali	1374	140.1	Cluster 48 : 140.10 ±13.43 (n=18)	-0.31	Cluster 48 : -0.31 ± 0.88 (n=18)	3	15	131.0%
211	R	Arghistan	Sartif Kalawal Kalai	241	142.9	Cluster 211 : 142.90 ±14.09 (n=17)	0.38	Cluster 211 : 0.38 ± 0.93 (n=17)	3	0	124.5%
205	R	Reg	Sardar Mohammad Naim Kalai	1770	144.2	Cluster 205 : 144.20 ±10.20 (n=11)	-1.73	Cluster 205 : -1.73 ± 0.60 (n=11)	8	14	124.3%
204	R	Reg	Moula Dad Mir Alam Ato kalai	1814	138.4	Cluster 204 : 138.40 ± 5.06 (n=7)	-1.96	Cluster 204 : -1.96 ± 0.10 (n=7)	9	13	121.3%
57	R	Zhari	Hajji fiaz Mohammad Aka	1722	130.8	Cluster 57 : 130.80 ± 6.82 (n=17)	-1.32	Cluster 57 : -1.32 ± 0.49 (n=17)	7	13	116.1%
45	R	Zhari	Painda	1140	140.2	Cluster 45 : 140.20 ±19.92 (n=11)	0.42	Cluster 45 : 0.42 ± 1.30 (n=14)	8	4	105.3%
216	R	Maruf	Angizai	1132	135.1	Cluster 216 : 135.10 ±12.52 (n=20)	-0.22	Cluster 216 : -0.22 ± 0.86 (n=20)	6	5	97.2%
28	R	Panjwayi	Madina	941	129.8	Cluster 28 : 129.80 ±13.91 (n=16)	-1.14	Cluster 28 : -1.14 ± 1.10 (n=15)	9	0	95.6%
203	R	Reg	Grang Sah	1713	143.4	Cluster 203 : 143.40 ± 7.50 (n=10)	-0.52	Cluster 203 : -0.52 ± 1.87 (n=9)	4	12	93.4%
33	R	Spin Boldak	Haji Mohmmad Mosa	2198	142.4	Cluster 33 : 142.40 ±14.43 (n=19)	0.20	Cluster 33 : 0.20 ± 0.85 (n=19)	3	17	91.0%
55	R	Zhari	Sanziray	1374	138.3	Cluster 55 : 138.30 ±12.16 (n=14)	-0.34	Cluster 55 : -0.34 ± 1.06 (n=14)	7	5	87.3%
37	R	Spin Boldak	Abdul	2044	148.5	Cluster 37 : 148.50 ± 9.55 (n=17)	0.23	Cluster 37 : 0.23 ± 0.59 (n=17)	0	17	83.2%
219	R	Maruf	Jalal	522	135.9	Cluster 219 : 135.90 ±10.21 (n=18)	-0.27	Cluster 219 : -0.27 ± 0.62 (n=17)	4	0	76.6%
52	R	Shaga	Fati khan Iwar mail	657	146.1	Cluster 52 : 146.10 ±12.88 (n=16)	0.60	Cluster 52 : 0.60 ± 1.38 (n=15)	5	0	76.1%
46	R	Zhari	Omarzai	1710	139.4	Cluster 46 : 139.40 ±14.34 (n=17)	-0.63	Cluster 46 : -0.63 ± 1.15 (n=17)	5	8	76.0%
17	R	Maywand	Sapozai	2100	141.1	Cluster 17 : 141.10 ±13.92 (n=15)	-0.72	Cluster 17 : -0.72 ± 1.65 (n=14)	5	10	71.4%

224	R	Nesh	Kochnai kariz	1142	143.0	Cluster 224 : 143.00 ±11.56 (n=14)	-0.21	Cluster 224 : -0.21 ± 0.91 (n=12)	4	4	70.1%
218	R	Maruf	Karim Kali	1080	138.2	Cluster 218 : 138.20 ±15.63 (n=16)	-0.12	Cluster 218 : -0.12 ± 0.99 (n=16)	7	0	64.8%
44	R	Zhari	Eid Gaah	1800	140.9	Cluster 44 : 140.90 ±13.71 (n=18)	-0.35	Cluster 44 : -0.35 ± 1.09 (n=15)	7	4	61.1%
27	R	Panjwayi	Haji Amanullah	1316	132.0	Cluster 27 : 132.00 ±11.56 (n=16)	-1.18	Cluster 27 : -1.18 ± 0.84 (n=14)	8	0	60.8%
13	R	Shawalikot	Haji Paio kalai	1349	148.9	Cluster 13 : 148.90 ±10.52 (n=9)	1.09	Cluster 13 : 1.09 ± 0.88 (n=8)	4	4	59.3%
212	R	Maruf	Lowar Shekhzai	1365	130.8	Cluster 212 : 130.80 ±10.98 (n=12)	-0.26	Cluster 212 : -0.26 ± 0.65 (n=12)	8	0	58.6%
209	R	Arghistan	Asakzai Kalai	528	136.6	Cluster 209 : 136.60 ± 7.94 (n=19)	-0.89	Cluster 209 : -0.89 ± 0.78 (n=19)	3	0	56.8%
23	R	Panjwayi	Chalghor kalai	917	142.8	Cluster 23 : 142.80 ±15.34 (n=18)	-0.10	Cluster 23 : -0.10 ± 1.03 (n=15)	5	0	54.5%
6	PD	Kandahar	Ganj Qalacha	735	151.8	Cluster 6 : 151.80 ±10.70 (n=16)	0.03	Cluster 6 : 0.03 ± 0.97 (n=14)	4	0	54.4%
10	R	Shawalikot	Wali kali	2427	134.3	Cluster 10 : 134.30 ±10.94 (n=16)	0.42	Cluster 10 : 0.42 ± 0.87 (n=16)	4	8	49.4%
25	R	Panjwayi	Taj Daar	821	133.6	Cluster 25 : 133.60 ±11.05 (n=18)	-0.43	Cluster 25 : -0.43 ± 0.94 (n=16)	4	0	48.7%
54	R	Panjwayi	Abdul Samad (Haji Baridad)	1054	138.9	Cluster 54 : 138.90 ±18.18 (n=17)	0.03	Cluster 54 : 0.03 ± 1.44 (n=15)	5	0	47.4%
39	R	Spin Boldak	Pakhwaran	1957	135.2	Cluster 39 : 135.20 ± 6.47 (n=18)	-0.79	Cluster 39 : -0.79 ± 0.77 (n=18)	3	6	46.0%
202	R	Khakriz	Hajji Dilbar Aka Kariz	704	140.6	Cluster 202 : 140.60 ±13.41 (n=18)	-0.21	Cluster 202 : -0.21 ± 1.09 (n=18)	3	0	42.6%
3	PD	Kandahar	Naw Deh	1652	147.7	Cluster 3 : 147.70 ±10.63 (n=19)	0.97	Cluster 3 : 0.97 ± 1.19 (n=18)	5	2	42.4%
51	R	Shaga	Fatawi kalai	1010	142.9	Cluster 51 : 142.90 ±11.41 (n=20)	0.50	Cluster 51 : 0.50 ± 1.14 (n=19)	4	0	39.6%
43	R	Spin Boldak	Mullah Rahmatullah kalai	2135	145.3	Cluster 43 : 145.30 ±14.73 (n=18)	-0.23	Cluster 43 : -0.23 ± 0.71 (n=17)	2	6	37.5%
7	R	Daman	Dai kalai	1366	136.5	Cluster 7 : 136.50 ± 9.79 (n=17)	-0.62	Cluster 7 : -0.62 ± 0.75 (n=17)	5	0	36.6%
58	R	Spin Boldak	Sidano kaly	1645	141.3	Cluster 58 : 141.30 ±12.50 (n=18)	-0.18	Cluster 58 : -0.18 ± 0.89 (n=18)	3	3	36.5%
26	R	Panjwayi	Abdul Ghani	2139	136.7	Cluster 26 : 136.70 ±13.19 (n=17)	-0.19	Cluster 26 : -0.19 ± 1.32 (n=17)	7	0	32.7%
24	R	Panjwayi	Gul Agha	1855	135.8	Cluster 24 : 135.80 ±11.14 (n=16)	-0.28	Cluster 24 : -0.28 ± 1.08 (n=14)	6	0	32.3%
30	R	Spin Boldak	Hazrat Bilal	2198	143.4	Cluster 30 : 143.40 ±12.52 (n=21)	0.14	Cluster 30 : 0.14 ± 0.91 (n=21)	4	3	31.8%
36	R	Spin Boldak	Haji Fida Mohammad	1572	144.7	Cluster 36 : 144.70 ±10.08 (n=14)	-0.35	Cluster 36 : -0.35 ± 1.35 (n=13)	5	0	31.8%
210	R	Arghistan	Popalzai	980	144.1	Cluster 210 : 144.10 ±16.47 (n=17)	0.37	Cluster 210 : 0.37 ± 1.00 (n=17)	3	0	30.6%
1	PD	Kandahar	Kakaro Gosh Khana	1330	146.9	Cluster 1 : 146.90 ±12.44 (n=17)	0.28	Cluster 1 : 0.28 ± 0.99 (n=17)	4	0	30.1%
222	R	Miya Nishin	Chako Gak	2693	149.6	Cluster 222 : 149.60 ±12.64 (n=17)	0.79	Cluster 222 : 0.79 ± 0.91 (n=16)	3	5	29.7%
206	R	Arghistan	Ali Khanzai	1831	134.8	Cluster 206 : 134.80 ±11.29 (n=20)	-0.92	Cluster 206 : -0.92 ± 0.86 (n=20)	5	0	27.3%
38	R	Spin Boldak	Mandai Palawan	1960	144.8	Cluster 38 : 144.80 ±10.93 (n=18)	-0.09	Cluster 38 : -0.09 ± 0.88 (n=17)	1	4	25.5%

34	R	Spin Boldak	Mirhamza Abdul Ghapor	2169	139.2	Cluster 34 : 139.20 ±15.46 (n=17)	0.00	Cluster 34 : 0.00 ± 1.03 (n=17)	5	0		23.1%
29	R	Spin Boldak	Haji God kalai	875	145.1	Cluster 29 : 145.10 ±15.13 (n=17)	-0.06	Cluster 29 : -0.06 ± 0.90 (n=17)	2	0		22.9%
14	R	Arghandab	Khwaja mulk	2472	146.6	Cluster 14 : 146.60 ±15.92 (n=16)	0.30	Cluster 14 : 0.30 ± 1.05 (n=17)	3	2		20.2%
41	R	Spin Boldak	Haji Akhtar Mohmmad	1083	153.7	Cluster 41 : 153.70 ±13.48 (n=19)	0.41	Cluster 41 : 0.41 ± 0.95 (n=18)	1	1		18.5%
214	R	Maruf	Sra Shela	11910	137.0	Cluster 214 : 137.00 ±11.05 (n=15)	-0.03	Cluster 214 : -0.03 ± 1.13 (n=14)	7	14		17.6%
8	R	Daman	Mandisar	3510	135.4	Cluster 8 : 135.40 ±14.29 (n=14)	-0.03	Cluster 8 : -0.03 ± 1.19 (n=13)	6	0		17.1%
32	R	Spin Boldak	Barkzo kalai	1281	138.8	Cluster 32 : 138.80 ±13.42 (n=17)	-0.38	Cluster 32 : -0.38 ± 1.01 (n=17)	2	0		15.6%
4	PD	Kandahar	Gundigan	1400	142.2	Cluster 4 : 142.20 ±10.87 (n=23)	-0.10	Cluster 4 : -0.10 ± 0.84 (n=23)	2	0		14.3%
31	R	Spin Boldak	Saheb Jaan	1488	150.1	Cluster 31 : 150.10 ± 9.50 (n=16)	0.59	Cluster 31 : 0.59 ± 0.61 (n=16)	2	0		13.4%
201	R	Khakriz	Khoshi Kalai	2044	145.8	Cluster 201 : 145.80 ±16.28 (n=18)	-0.15	Cluster 201 : -0.15 ± 1.00 (n=18)	2	0		9.8%
40	R	Spin Boldak	Tora sagi	2156	148.8	Cluster 40 : 148.80 ±11.13 (n=13)	-0.52	Cluster 40 : -0.52 ± 1.17 (n=12)	2	0		9.3%
207	R	Arghistan	Narin Wala	1148	143.5	Cluster 207 : 143.50 ±10.37 (n=19)	-0.18	Cluster 207 : -0.18 ± 0.84 (n=19)	1	0		8.7%
221	R	Miya Nishin	Low Tala Kalai	3812	138.8	Cluster 221 : 138.80 ±10.98 (n=19)	0.44	Cluster 221 : 0.44 ± 0.99 (n=17)	3	0		7.9%
15	R	Arghandab	Nagahan kossa	1300	147.7	Cluster 15 : 147.40 ±11.67 (n=16)	-0.03	Cluster 15 : -0.03 ± 1.16 (n=15)	1	0		7.7%
42	R	Spin Boldak	Mohmmad Esa	1750	153.3	Cluster 42 : 153.30 ±11.10 (n=18)	0.14	Cluster 42 : 0.14 ± 0.83 (n=17)	1	0		5.7%
50	R	Zhari	Sdeequllah Dasht	1850	145.4	Cluster 50 : 145.40 ± 9.96 (n=13)	0.94	Cluster 50 : 0.94 ± 0.76 (n=13)	1	0		5.4%
56	R	Spin Boldak	Delai Shora Rabat	2170	146.7	Cluster 56 : 146.70 ±11.73 (n=18)	0.37	Cluster 56 : 0.37 ± 1.03 (n=18)	1	0		4.6%
53	PD	Kandahar	Mohmmad Gul Qalacha	2205	154.8	Cluster 53 : 154.80 ± 7.49 (n=19)	0.06	Cluster 53 : 0.06 ± 0.87 (n=18)	0	1		4.5%
220	R	Miya Nishin	Paynawa Zamto	2671	148.4	Cluster 220 : 148.40 ±13.68 (n=19)	0.14	Cluster 220 : 0.14 ± 1.34 (n=17)	1	0		3.7%
2	PD	Kandahar	Zakar Sharef	10000	147.8	Cluster 2 : 147.80 ±15.27 (n=16)	-0.30	Cluster 2 : -0.30 ± 1.27 (n=16)	3	0		3.0%
16	R	Arghandab	Dhast masjid	1400	143.1	Cluster 16 : 143.10 ± 9.18 (n=16)	0.44	Cluster 16 : 0.44 ± 0.85 (n=14)	0	0		0.0%
208	R	Arghistan	Da Sar Kalai	1767	145.2	Cluster 208 : 145.20 ± 8.97 (n=18)	-0.25	Cluster 208 : -0.25 ± 0.72 (n=18)	0	0		0.0%
5	PD	Kandahar	Ghulam Dastageer Qalacha	1932	158.3	Cluster 5 : 158.30 ± 8.85 (n=18)	0.21	Cluster 5 : 0.21 ± 0.77 (n=18)	0	0		0.0%

Taking into consideration that we do not have at present enough information from the districts of Ghorak and Shorabak (grey zones) we developed the following map of the provincial districts according to assessed emergency priority in the present survey.

- Dark Red = Priority Highest
- Red = „ High
- Orange = „ Medium
- Yellow = „ Average
- Grey = Not enough data available at the moment

To be clear this does NOT mean in any way that the lesser priority districts are not in need of humanitarian help. There is there high prevalence of chronic malnutrition as well as multiple gaps on other instances to be addressed. Our meaning is limited to acute malnutrition and in this respect we suggest to address emergency intervention, as much as feasible, toward the identified more affected clusters/districts.

Regarding the “grey areas”, as common practice, it is suggested to infer the data from the neighboring clusters, which in this case translate in considering at high to highest priority also the two districts of Ghorak and Shorabak.

9. Conclusions

The level of Acute Malnutrition in Kandahar Province as a whole is near or over the conventional emergency levels for GAM and for SAM (15% for GAM and 3% for SAM) both when considered as based on MUAC alone and even more when considered as Combined Acute Malnutrition.

We agree that the use of the prevalence based on Combined Acute Malnutrition, both General and Severe, can be more useful to identify people needs and when utilized for planning emergency nutrition humanitarian interventions.

There can be slightly different approaches to calculate Combined Acute Malnutrition and its Confidence Intervals, and it will be useful to implement more advanced statistical calculations in future ENA software to automatise and render more “statistically solid” the related outcomes.

The level of Acute Malnutrition is very-low in Kandahar city as a whole, whilst it is high in rural communities. However there will be probably “pockets” of high prevalence of acute malnutrition even in Kandahar city.

There is a high prevalence (around 18%) of Non-residents within the Kandahar population, generally intermingled with the host communities. These Non-residents can reach percentage of over 25% in areas near to active conflict zones and are mainly represented by IDPs.

The Non-resident part of the Kandahar population shows a higher prevalence of Acute Malnutrition compared to the Residents’ one.

Mortality in Kandahar as a whole is at middle-high level for children under age of five (1.14/10k/die) and at high level for adults (0.96/10k/die) where it approaches the conventional emergency level of 1/10,000/day. The high adult mortality affects the male adult population and is linked to trauma/injury.

Multiple parameters in our assessment depict a situation of need not only in regard to nutrition but also related to Health and Nutrition Awareness, Health Education, WASH and Food Security.

The distribution of Acute Malnutrition (and of Chronic Malnutrition as well) in Kandahar province is not-normal showing relevant dis-homogeneity within different clusters. “Pockets” (i.e. clusters/villages) of high Acute Malnutrition does exist with significantly higher prevalence of GAM/SAM.

These Pockets of Malnutrition seems to be generally associated with higher prevalence of Non-resident population (as well as with worst parameters in terms of Health Education, WASH and Food Security).

The geographical pattern of the Pockets of Malnutrition is loosely associated with the districts topography.

The “two phases” approach to an assessment of this sort in an environment as dangerous as the Kandahar province of Afghanistan has shown to be effective in terms of feasibility and in mitigating the risks for the field personnel. However in future assessments of this sort the chronologic distance between the two phases must be reduced as much as possible.

10. Recommendations

It is recommended to implement as soon as possible emergency humanitarian action to mitigate the serious situation of acute malnutrition and high mortality in the Kandahar province. Despite fine humanitarian countermeasures by the local in-line Departments, the BPHS implementer and both national and international NGOs the situation resulting from the recent intensification of the conflict, high influx of IDPs from neighbouring provinces (Helmand and Uruzgan mainly) and high influx of Documented and Undocumented Returnees from Pakistan, acting on a substrate whose resilience has been weakened to the limit by the longest armed conflict in recent history, is creating the premises for a humanitarian catastrophe. The previewed restart of Returnees high influx from Pakistan in March 2017 is marking the necessary level of emergency to put in place pre-emptive measures. In our assessment we already measured a 17.3 % prevalence of IDPs within this population reaching 20.5% with the Returnees (both types). **No one health system can face an increase in catchment population of +20% without stress and especially cannot support such increase the present already overwhelmed health system of Kandahar province.** The local humanitarian actors, IOs, NGOs and GOA agencies, needs support to mitigate as much as possible this situation. The BARAN NGO, BPHS implementer in the whole province, in particular, needs help and technical support in its role of responsible of the health of 2.5 million people. Not only BARAN financial budgetary resources (calculated on a catchment population of 1.1 million people, which at present is more than doubled) are not in line with the present needs, but also its managerial capacity can be hopefully improved by a “on the job” training performed by a non-invasive, non-academic actor supporting its action in one of the more delicate and relevant sector of present day Afghanistan: the one of Acute Malnutrition and avoidable morbidity and mortality, especially asking its toll on the weakest part of society, the mothers and children of this Country. This not to speak of the permanent disabilities on physical and mental development which are the well known dire consequences of Chronic Malnutrition.

With this assessment we have demonstrated a high level of Acute Malnutrition, surpassing the emergency prevalence threshold of 15% when calculated as comprehensive index from MUAC, WHZ and oedema. General as well as Under 5 mortality are also high and the under 5 Mortality is likely to include the majority of avoidable deaths resulting directly or indirectly from malnutrition. Chronic Malnutrition is also at very high levels seriously hindering the future development capacities of the new generations. We also registered a high number of violent deaths, mainly of young males and also a number of violent deaths in children.

What we observed in our sample is a coalescence of factors all likely to contribute to the final outcome of Malnutrition and Mortality: **low food access, consumption and security, bad hygienic conditions in the WASH sector, low knowledge of basic hygienic practices, relevance of vaccinations and benefits of correct breastfeeding plus, on top of it, low awareness of the symptoms, signs, dangers, preventable measures and cure of malnutrition.**

By segregating different categorical variables within our sample we tried to better identify causes and therefore priorities where to address an humanitarian action. We observed **higher prevalence of acute malnutrition in Rural versus Urban settlements and in Non-residents (IDP and Returnees) versus Residents households.** Cross matching prevalence of acute malnutrition with prevalence of non residents (IDP and Returnees) we were able to identify a pattern were the two variables were going on a parallel way, **The higher the percentages of non-residents the higher the prevalence of malnutrition.**

Those people, mainly IDPs, reaching 25% of prevalence in the external part of the province, on the Border with area of active conflict, are desperate families flying from war and deprived of all. They are mixed within a host community which in turn is already in a precarious situation.

We have listed the villages included in our sample in a priority order based on higher malnutrition and higher percentage of IDP and we found that geo-mapping the villages more in need a pattern can be identified with the Districts of **Maywand, Nesh, Reg** as the more in need, with a probable high level of priority also in the adjacent districts of **Ghorack and Shorabak**. High priority is also identified in the districts of **Zhari, Daman, Maruf** and then the others following. Humanitarian intervention planning shall balance identified needs with practical feasibility in terms of accessibility and especially security.

In all cases we INTERSOS and HRDA humanitarian agencies **do recommend an emergency humanitarian action to fight Malnutrition and Mortality in the more in needs Districts of Kandahar Province to be implemented ASAP**. Given the context of multiple factors contributing to the end result of Malnutrition and Mortality we recommend **an holistic, comprehensive humanitarian initiative including Clinic Nutritional, WASH and Food Security actions, all of them under the fundamental umbrella of Education** to obtain the necessary knowledge and therefore fundamental awareness from the affected people.

Apart this main recommendation we also recommend:

To implement the calculation of combined Acute Malnutrition in further SMART assessment and to include these calculation, with strong statistical background, in future ENA software release.

In doing SMART assessment at Provincial level in Afghanistan to be able to segregate data from different clusters or groups of clusters, as well as from different class of households (e.g. Host community versus Non-residents) in order to better understand and plan the following humanitarian actions.

Even doing so, however, the inherent characteristics of a SMART assessment at provincial level in Afghanistan will have a great chance to include a great level of dis-homogeneity. To assess for health and nutrition related projects we think that assessments performed at district, or group of homogeneous districts level will have more chance to be statistically solid and informant on a larger set of parameters.

We also suggest to include as much as possible in future SMART assessment questions aimed to explore the reasons for malnutrition, i.e. questions upon Food Security, WASH and Health Education. This is because only identifying the causes, i.e. the ethiology of malnutrition, we shall be capacitated to fight them. And only treating the causes one can eventually reach the target of exit from emergency. Taking care of the “first-aid” phase only (the RUTF) has the capacity to “chronicize” but not to solve the emergency.

In other words we suggest to focus on people, with their environment and their problems, not to focus on “clusters” or “sectors” of intervention. The problem is not “the malnutrition” (or the FS, the APC, the ESNFI, etc.) the problem is the malnourished, unhealthy, unprotected, impoverished people.

The last recommendation is to do less assessments and to do more projects. People of Afghanistan has already seen - and is still seeing - a really huge amount of assessments

of all sorts. In front of that, the amount of budget made available for projects by IO and donors is continuously shrinking. Frankly speaking it is not so necessary to do an assessment to understand that the situation in Afghanistan is at “disaster” level. Assessments shall be done to do project proposals, hopefully better projects proposals. So we think that ideally each assessment shall be followed by a project (or - at least - by a project proposal).

11. Ethical consideration

This assessment protocol has been checked according the INTERSOS and HRDA ethical codes finding no impediments to its realization

The dignity of all people involved in this assessment has been maintained, and the identity of people assessed in the exercise has not and it will not be revealed in any form.

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13. Appendices (Annexed)

- 1) Questionnaires in Pashtun and English
- 2) Field instruction for enumerators in Pashtun and English
- 3) FCS HDDS HHS tables
- 4) Standardization test of enumerators training
- 5) Result Tables for NCHS growth reference 1977
- 6) SMART Plausibility Report
- 7) BARAN NGO last 3 years SAM-OPD activity
- 8) OCHA WWW Operational Presence Dec 2016
- 9) Presence of Health Services “white areas” Handmade Map
- 10) Training schedule
- 11) Results of Phase 1
- 12) List of Villages and PDs with population size for cluster selection